

CONDUCTIVITY IN A HONEYCOMB
SACHDEV-YE-KITAEV LATTICE

LEITFÄHIGKEIT EINES SACHDEV-YE-KITAEV MODELLS AUF
DEM HONIGWABENGITTER

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ABSTRACT

Despite considerable theoretical effort, there has been no consensus on the description of the strange metal state seen in high temperature superconductors and its linear in T resistivity. Here, we construct a simple solvable model of itinerant electrons interacting through random couplings on a honeycomb lattice composed of Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev quantum dots which describes electrons without quasiparticle excitations. This model is solvable in the large- N limit and displays a temperature dependant crossover between two regimes. By tuning the strength of this interaction relative to the bandwidth of the itinerant electrons, we can additionally obtain a finite T crossover to a fully incoherent regime that also has a linear in T resistivity. In the non-Fermi liquid regime, the dc resistivity increases linearly with temperature over a broad range of temperatures. The self energy has a singular frequency dependence but lacks momentum dependence which is reminiscent of a dynamical mean-field-theory-like behavior but in dimensions $d < \infty$ [17]. In the low-temperature and strong-coupling limit, the behaviour parallels that of Dirac fermions. We discuss the implications of these results and further possibilities in such studies.

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INTRODUCTION

The Fermi liquid picture has been a key concept in the analysis of matter at a quantum level since its conception by Landau in 1956 [43]. Despite the general success of the idea, recent experiments [6, 14] have made it clear that this quasiparticle picture is insufficient. The observation of non-Fermi liquid regimes has led to the question: "How do we describe materials that do not admit a quasiparticle analysis?" Understanding the behaviour of non-Fermi liquids has now become an important problem in condensed matter physics.

Many of these exotic phenomena that are indescribable by the quasiparticle picture are found in strongly correlated materials like the cuprates [6], pnictides, ruthenates and heavy-fermion materials. One of the most interesting features of these materials is an anomalous linear in T resistivity¹ for a wide range of temperatures. Recently, the experimental study of twisted bilayer graphene also known as magic angle graphene [13–15], has also depicted the existence of such an anomalous state. In this material, the interesting physics has been observed when the two layers of graphene are at specific "magic" angles, and the linear in T resistivity is observed for a fairly large range in temperature. This poses further questions about the importance of lattice structure or geometry to the understanding of the strange metal regime. To clarify, the term "strange" metal is a blanket expression to describe a wide variety of materials exhibiting the anomalous behaviour described here. The underlying cause for their "strange" behaviour is not unique.

These strange metal states are ubiquitous in modern quantum materials. Field theories to explain the theory of strange metals have mostly focused on models without disorder, where the Fermi surfaces are coupled to gapless bosonic excitations. This leads to a breakdown of the quasiparticle excitations near the Fermi surface, but leave the surface intact [24]. Experiments [61] have however, indicated that disorder effects are likely important. In addition, the literature on quantum transport has not really advanced in the study of conduction in systems that possibly do not admit the quasiparticle picture (e.g. a disordered conducting metallic state with the order of electron-electron scattering smaller than that of lattice impurity scattering [34]). Most transport equations stem from the idea of a quasiparticle implicitly assumed. Simply put, there is, at the moment, no clear interpretation in quantum matter to describe these disordered, non-quasiparticle, metallic states.

¹ as opposed to $\rho \propto T^2$.

In the past few years, the study of the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev (SYK) model [41, 63, 66] has advanced our capability to describe states without quasiparticles. Initially proposed to solve the problem of the Heisenberg anti-ferromagnet, it was recently understood and adapted to be an effective, albeit incomplete approach to understanding the behaviour of non-Fermi liquids, and particularly that of the strange metal phase. In short, the SYK model describes the interaction of fermions with a random pairwise entangled all-to-all interaction. This SYK model has many interesting features, including the absence of quasiparticles, and being solvable in the large N limit, in the presence of disorder at low temperatures. At the moment, they are the simplest model to fulfil this, and are ideal to use as a quantum building block for theories of strange metals in non-zero spatial dimensions.

In this thesis, we present a simple model of itinerant electrons, interacting through randomized couplings. In addition, these electrons are localized on a honeycomb lattice array of quantum dots, each dot described by the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev model. The model is solvable in the large- N limit. We will calculate the conductivity of the system, and observe whether there exists a change in behaviour with respect to a crossover temperature scale. Studies have been performed [17], to understand these systems in the presence of a critical Fermi surface. Here, we turn to a lattice that does not exhibit such a surface and instead admits Dirac points.

Before diving into the construction of such a model and computing the transport coefficient, we have first summarized the concept of quasiparticles in quantum matter in [Chapter 2](#). After briefly describing the breakdown of such systems, [Chapter 3](#) presents an introduction to the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev model from a purely condensed matter perspective. More details on its relevance to AdS/CFT and black holes can be found through [34, 63]. [Chapter 4](#) then describes the study of quantum transport and how we have currently adapted their ideas to describe regimes where quasiparticles may not exist.

[Chapter 5](#) then introduces the core of the thesis, where we construct a model on a honeycomb lattice with the help of SYK dots. [Chapter 6](#) proceeds to further the setup, wherein the full propagator of the system is derived in order for us to setup the calculation of the dc conductivity. The conductivity is then calculated in [Chapter 7](#). The thesis is then discussed and an outlook is finally presented in [Chapter 8](#).

Part I

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO CONCEPTS IN QUANTUM TRANSPORT

In [Part i](#) of this thesis, we introduce quantum matter with and without quasiparticles within a historical context. The Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev model is introduced from a condensed matter perspective. In addition, quantum transport with reference to the previous topics is discussed.

QUANTUM MATTER

2.1 QUANTUM MATTER WITH QUASIPARTICLES

2.1.1 *The quasiparticle concept*

The quasiparticle concept has been a key idea for many successful theories in condensed matter physics, by allowing us to simplify many difficult quantum mechanical many-body problems. Examples of such successes include:

- Fermi liquid theory applicable to metals, insulators and semiconductors [59];
- Fractional quantum Hall states, where the quasiparticles are highly non-trivial combinations of the underlying electrons¹;
- Theory of superconductivity (i.e pairing of quasiparticles) [5, 9, 18, 74] ; and the
- Theory of metals in one dimension² - Luttinger-Tomonaga Liquids [31, 45, 73].

But what are these quasiparticles? - They are emergent phenomena that occur when a microscopically complicated system such as a solid, behaves as if it contained different weakly interacting particles in free space. They can be described as "an excited bulk" in a many electron state which responds like an ordinary particle. When a real particle moves through a system, it pushes or pulls on neighboring particles, creating a cloud of agitated particles. The cloud along with the real particle constitute the quasiparticle. The particle cloud "screens" the real particle, such that the quasiparticles themselves only weakly interact with each other (Figure 2.1).

The concept of quasiparticles allows us to mathematically transform the complicated motion of the real particles (in a solid, for example) into the much simpler motion of imagined quasiparticles, which behave more like non-interacting particles. How do we do this? In a typical quantum many-body

¹ These quasiparticles also carry exotic quantum numbers such as fractional charge, and obey fractional statistics

² Here, the quasiparticles we refer to are not restricted to fermions. Collective modes are also defined to be quasiparticles.

Figure 2.1: An illustration of the quasiparticle concept [47].

system, it is difficult to understand the entire spectrum of a theory that has an extensive number of particles and a corresponding exponentially large number of eigenstates. However, since we are usually interested only in the low energy physics of the system, we can restrict ourselves to studying the low energy subspace of the spectrum, where these states are known to have a particle-like description with a relatively long lifetime [59, 62].

Many parts of the following discussion of quantum matter with and without quasiparticles has been adapted from the talks and presentations given by Subir Sachdev, which can be found here [61]³.

Mathematically, a defining trait of quasiparticles is that they are additive excitations. Generally, without considering translation symmetry or a well-defined momentum space, the low-lying excitations of the many-body system can be identified as a set $\{n_\alpha\}$ of quasiparticles with energies $\{\varepsilon_\alpha\}$. The low energy spectrum can then be written as

$$E = \sum_{\alpha} n_{\alpha} \varepsilon_{\alpha} + \sum_{\alpha, \beta} F_{\alpha\beta} n_{\alpha} n_{\beta} + O(n^3), \quad (2.1)$$

where $F_{\alpha, \beta}$ is known as the Landau parameter and $O(n^3)$ represents higher order interaction terms, which are typically irrelevant to the physics of the system [24, 61, 75]. In a lattice system of N sites, this creates a polynomial

³ Particularly, the talks given at the Les Houches Summer School (Aug 19-21, 2019) and at Fudan University (Jul 11, 2018)

parameterization of the energy of $\sim e^{\alpha N}$ states. However, these states are not really measurable experimentally.

In any system of this nature, we can assume that the quasiparticles would eventually collide with one another. Such collisions eventually lead to the process of thermal equilibration in a chaotic quantum state, but this can take an extremely long time. This also leads to the "death" of the quasiparticle. To test whether a quasiparticle is long lived, we can compute their lifetime. In the example of a Fermi liquid, quasiparticle-quasiparticle scattering takes place which allows us to utilize Fermi's Golden Rule [67]. At low temperatures, the lifetime of a quasiparticle at the Fermi energy diverges as

$$\tau_{eq} \sim \frac{E_F}{T^2}, \quad (2.2)$$

where E_F is the Fermi energy. This shows us that the quasiparticle has an extremely long lifespan at low temperatures. Note that the above computation assumes a constant spectral density in the vicinity of the Fermi level. Singularities in the density of states would lead to a different scaling behavior, which can be seen in the SYK Model discussed below, for example.

Next, we take a look at an approach to study a simple model of a metal with quasiparticles.

2.1.2 A metal with quasiparticles

A simple model of a metal with quasiparticles can be described with the following Hamiltonian:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_{ij} c_i^\dagger c_j, \quad (2.3)$$

where c^\dagger and c are the fermionic creation and annihilation operators of a particle at a given lattice site i or j , following the anti-commutation relations

$$\{c_i, c_j\} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \{c_i, c_j^\dagger\} = \delta_{ij}, \quad (2.4)$$

and the hopping parameters t_{ij} are independent Gaussian random variables obeying the following conditions:

$$\overline{t_{ij}} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{|t_{ij}|^2} = t^2. \quad (2.5)$$

Here, it is assumed a fraction $Q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_i^\dagger c_i$ of the sites are filled, and that the electrons move randomly between the lattice sites one-by-one.

In order to investigate properties of the (physical) system, we must "interact" with it. We can either look at the problem of the interaction of states of an

isolated system (e.g scattering problems), or we can attempt to understand the physical properties of a system from the "outside", considering the role of small perturbations. The general approach for the latter is known as a linear response theory, where the results are usually representable in terms of susceptibilities, which can, typically, be experimentally measured. In both cases, all quantities of physical interest such as the conductivity, can be derived from a suitably defined correlation function or propagator.

To obtain the Green's function, we perform a Feynman graph expansion. Averaging with respect to the hopping parameter yields the following exact relations in the large N limit:

$$G(i\omega) = \frac{1}{i\omega + \mu - \Sigma(i\omega)}, \quad \Sigma(\tau) = t^2 G(\tau), \quad (2.6)$$

for the Green's function and self energy, respectively. Obtaining these equations are not obvious [1]. A detailed calculation for a more complicated case is discussed in Section 3.2 and in Appendix A.

Briefly, the Green's function or propagator, is a function that specifies the probability amplitude for a particle to travel from one place to another in a given time, or to travel with a certain energy and momentum. The self energy is the energy that a particle has as a result of changes that it itself causes in its environment and it represents the contribution to the particle's own energy due to interactions between the particle and its system [1]. In the context of condensed matter physics, relevant to the movement of electrons in a material, the self energy represents the potential felt by the electron due to the interactions of the surrounding medium with the electron. Since electrons repel each other, the moving electron polarizes or acts as the cause to displace the electrons in its vicinity, thereby changing the potential of the moving electron fields.

In this case, let ε_α be the eigenvalues for the matrix $\frac{t_{ij}}{\sqrt{N}}$. The fermions will occupy the lowest $Q * N$ eigenvalues, below the Fermi energy E_F . The density of states is then

$$\rho(\omega) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\alpha} \delta(\omega - \varepsilon_{\alpha}). \quad (2.7)$$

This would indicate that the spacing between the eigenvalues is ε_α and, hence the spacing of the ground state quasiparticle excitations would be of the order $\frac{1}{N}$. In contrast, there are 2^N many body levels with energy $E = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N n_{\alpha} \varepsilon_{\alpha}$, with $n_{\alpha} = 0, 1$, and we would naively expect the many body level spacing to be of the order 2^{-N} [24, 26, 54, 61].

So far, we have assumed that the system is free from interactions, which typically not the case in physical systems. Let us see what happens when weak

interactions are added to the system. The Hamiltonian is then modified and looks like the following:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{i,j=1}^N t_{ij} c_i^\dagger c_j + \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{i,j,k,l=1}^N J_{ij;kl} c_i^\dagger c_j^\dagger c_k c_l, \quad (2.8)$$

where $J_{ij;kl}$ are independent random variables with

$$\overline{J_{ij;kl}} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{|J_{ij;kl}|^2} = J^2. \quad (2.9)$$

The lifetime of the quasiparticle, τ_α , can be computed for an exact eigenstate $\psi_\alpha(k)$ of the free particle Hamiltonian with energy E_α . Using Fermi's golden rule⁴ for E_α at the Fermi energy we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tau_\alpha} &= \pi J_c^2 \rho_0^2 \int dE_\beta dE_\gamma dE_\delta f(E_\beta)(1 - f(E_\gamma)) \\ &\quad \cdot (1 - f(E_\delta)) \delta(E_\alpha + E_\beta - E_\gamma - E_\delta), \\ &= \frac{\pi^3 J^2 \rho_0^2}{4} T^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where ρ_0 is the density of states at the Fermi energy. The solution to the integral come from averaging over the distribution for fermions⁵ [16]. This is a description of the Fermi liquid state wherein the two-body interactions lead to a scattering time of quasiparticle excitations which diverge proportional to T^{-2} at the Fermi level as outlined in the previous subsection. This approach however, is not useful for all systems, as we will see in the following section.

The implication that Fermi liquid theory is not universally applicable tells us that there is a point where the approach breaks down. Let us briefly summarize key points in the Fermi liquid theory, in order to better appreciate how we can describe systems where it fails. A detailed description of Fermi liquid theory can be found in [59]. A discussion of the theory with respect to how it breaks down can be found in [62, 75], from which the section below is adapted.

2.1.3 Landau's Fermi liquid theory

The quasiparticle idea discussed in Section 2.1 is an important concept that originates from Landau's Fermi liquid theory [43]. The Fermi liquid is probably the most well-known quantum many-body state in condensed matter physics. The characteristics of the theory can be easily understood in a simple free fermion picture, such as the system mentioned in Section 2.1.2. In accordance

⁴ $\Gamma_{i \rightarrow f} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle f | H' | i \rangle|^2 \rho(E_F)$, where H' is the Hamiltonian considering the effect of small perturbations to the system.

⁵ Fermi-Dirac distribution

with Pauli's exclusion principle, non-interacting fermions occupy the lowest energy single particle states. This leads to the concept of a Fermi surface: a surface in momentum space separating the empty and occupied single fermion states [62]. Then, the lowest energy excitations are quasiparticle excitations, which behave in a particle-like manner outside the Fermi surface, and in a hole-like manner within the Fermi surface. Landau's Fermi liquid theory can be understood as a careful justification for the stability of this simple system in the presence of (weak) interactions between fermions. Interactions are expected to modify the wavefunction of the quasiparticle, however, they do not destabilize their integrity.

Figure 2.2: Example of Fermi surfaces: (hole and electron doped) cuprate superconductors [62]

For a Fermi liquid, the Green's function can be written as

$$G(i\omega, \mathbf{k}) \sim \frac{Z}{i\omega + \mu - \varepsilon(\mathbf{k})} \quad (2.11)$$

where μ is the chemical potential and $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})$ is the energy corresponding to the momentum state. The value Z is known as the quasiparticle residue and is very characteristic of Fermi liquid theory. Physically, we can say that a propagating fermion interacts with its surrounding in such a way that the net effect of the interactions is to make the fermion behave as a "dressed" fermion, altering its dynamical properties. These "dressed" fermions are what we think of as "quasiparticles", and Z represents the magnitude of this "dressing".

Why is the Fermi liquid theory useful? An important concept underlying the theory is that of analyticity. That is, states with the same symmetry can be adiabatically connected [11, 75]. This is advantageous, since it suggests that when presented with a difficult problem, it may be possible to guess a simpler problem presenting the needed solution. This is because analyticity implies that we can obtain the eigenstates of the required Hamiltonian perturbatively

from that of a simpler Hamiltonian with the same symmetries⁶ (independent of whether we can actually carry out the calculation or not). Also, as a result, the correlation and the response functions of the harder problem bear a one-to-one correspondence with the simpler problem in their analytic properties.

How do we guess the simpler problem? Experiments often provide an intuition as to what the right simple problem may be⁷. For example, to study a system of interacting electrons within the metallic range of densities, the simpler problem is that of the kinetic energy of particles with Fermi statistics. Illustrating this, we can start with non-interacting fermions, and then turn on the interactions. The qualitative behavior of the system does not change as long as the system does not go through (or is close to) a phase transition. For further discussion, Appendix F in [49] has a well presented construction of the Fermi liquid theory.

2.1.3.1 Breakdown in the Fermi Liquid Theory

From Landau's phenomenological theory, we can only see that the theory breaks down when the physical properties, such as the compressibility, or the magnetic susceptibility, diverge or when the collective modes representing oscillations of the Fermi surface become unstable. The latter are called the Landau-Pomeranchuk singularities[44] and occur when the Landau parameters $F_{\alpha,\beta}$ reach a critical value. We can make a more general statement that Landau theory breaks down when the quasiparticle residue⁸ Z related to the interaction of the system becomes zero. This can occur if the interaction in terms of the number of particle-hole pairs diverges. Simply put, the addition of a particle or a hole to the system creates a divergent number of particle-hole pairs in the system such that the leading term does not have a finite weight in the thermodynamic limit. This would necessitate that the self-energy be singular as a function of ω near the Fermi level [75]. This in turn means that the Green's functions of singular Fermi liquids contain branch cuts rather than poles unlike Landau Fermi liquids. The weakest singularity of this kind is encountered in the borderline "marginal Fermi liquids" where

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{k}_F, \omega) \sim \omega \ln \frac{\omega_c}{\omega} + i|\omega|. \quad (2.12)$$

If a divergent number of low-energy particle-hole pairs are created upon the addition of a bare particle, it means that the low-energy response functions of

⁶ However, eigenstates of the same time, but with different symmetries cannot be obtained through continuation of the given state

⁷ It may not always be simple to guess a simpler problem, e.g Bogoliubov problem [10] or the Kondo problem[52]

⁸ or the related quantity, quasiparticle amplitude

these non-Fermi liquids are also divergent. The form of self-energy displayed by this marginal Fermi liquid state cannot be obtained from the quasiparticle idea from Fermi liquid theory. In addition, this marginal Fermi liquid theory postulates the existence of marginally defined quasiparticles, whose scattering rate is comparable to their energy. Experimental studies of the high T_C superconductors have consistently seen a regime in which the Fermi liquid theory is inapplicable and physical properties, that would arise from the marginal Fermi liquid self energy stated above appear. How would we construct a theory for such a state? It makes sense to step away from Landau's Fermi liquid theory approach and consider alternatives. In strongly correlated materials, for example, the elementary excitations are so far from being independent that it seems likely that quasiparticles cannot be used as a starting point. The next step would then be to construct a system where quasiparticles do not exist!

The following sections describing quantum matter without quasiparticles has been partially adapted from [34].

2.2 SOME HISTORIC CONTEXT

Since the discovery of high T_C superconductors [6], an ubiquitous property seen is the anomalous 'strange metal' state (in the cuprates and pnictides, for example), found at temperatures, above the superconducting critical temperature, T_C [65].

Their transport properties deviate heavily from those of conventional metals described by Fermi liquid theory, and spectral probes have shown an absence of long-lived quasiparticle excitations. The value of T_C can be typically determined by identifying the stability between the free energies of the superconductor and the strange metal phases. Hence, to formulate a theory of high T_C superconductivity, an understanding of the strange metal regime is a necessity. This is the primary motivation in developing a solid understanding of the theory of strange metals in condensed matter. Broadly speaking, we can consider the strange metal as an important realization of a state of quantum matter without quasiparticles. While we are aware that no quasiparticle description exists to understand the phase of quantum matter of interest to us, this definition is rather unsatisfactory since we can not definitively establish whether a particular state is truly quasiparticle-free.

What would be the best way to construct or verify whether a proposed system is devoid of quasiparticles? Currently the best approaches are to look at the time the system takes to attain thermal equilibrium. From Eq.(2.10), we are aware that in a Fermi liquid, the quasiparticle lifetime diverges as $\tau_{eq} \sim T^{-2}$. In

Figure 2.3: A schematic phase diagram of hole-doped cuprates, as a function of hole-doping p and temperature T . Image adapted from [32]. Here, AF represents the anti-ferromagnetic phase, PG is the pseudo-gap phase, DW is density wave, dSC is the d-wave superconducting region, and SM is the strange metal regime. T_C stands for the superconducting transition temperature.

[62], after examining a variety of models with or without quasiparticles it was proposed that there is a lower bound

$$\tau_{eq} \geq C \frac{\hbar}{k_B T}, \quad (2.13)$$

which is obeyed by all infinite many-body quantum systems as $T \rightarrow 0$, where C is a dimensionless $O(1)$ number, independent of T . This is known as the Planckian timescale, and highlights the importance of quantum fluctuations in quantum many-body studies. This provides us with an answer to the question: "How short can we make the equilibration time τ in a system without quasiparticles?". Viewing the picture from this dynamic perspective, we can conclude that states with quasiparticles are expected to have a long τ_{eq} , while those without quasiparticles have a short τ_{eq} , giving us two distinct regimes.

2.3 QUANTUM MATTER WITHOUT QUASIPARTICLES

The simplest examples of systems without quasiparticle excitations are realized in quantum matter at special densities which are commensurate with an underlying lattice [62]. These are typically modeled using quantum field theories which are particle-hole symmetric, and have a vanishing value of a conserved $U(1)$ charge linked to the particle number of the lattice model — hence known

as ‘zero’ density. Even in these lattice models, it is conventional to measure the particle density in terms of deviations from such a commensurate density.

In particular, a simple system modeled by the above mentioned zero density quantum field theory is graphene [22]. This quantum field theory is, quite interestingly, relativistic at low energies. Graphene is a model described by a honeycomb lattice of carbon atoms, and all the important electronic excitations are observed to reside on a single π -orbital on each atom. The ‘zero’ density here, corresponds to a density of one electron per atom. The computation of the band structure of free electrons for this configuration yields an electronic dispersion identical to that of massless 2-component Dirac fermions with 4 "flavor" indices, which indicate the sub-lattice, spin and position of Dirac cones in the Brillouin zone.

Figure 2.4: Lattice structure of graphene, image adapted from [50].

The density of electrons can be varied by applying a chemical potential, μ , such that the dispersion is $\varepsilon(k) = v_F|k| - \mu$, where v_F is the Fermi velocity [50]. Electronic states with $\varepsilon(k) < 0$ are occupied at absolute zero, and the zero density here corresponds to the state where no potential is applied, i.e. $\mu = 0$. At first glance, it would appear that graphene is completely described by the quasiparticle picture. There are instantaneous non-local Coulomb interactions between the electrons because the velocity of light $c \gg v_F$. These interactions are irrelevant at low energies under the renormalization group, and hence the electronic quasiparticles are well-defined⁹. However, as can be seen in [23,

⁹ A detailed discussion on the electronic properties of graphene can be found in [50], while the field theoretic analysis of graphene is outlined in [22]

28], the interactions become weak only logarithmically slowly (mimicking the singularity described in [Section 2.1.3.1](#)), and hence there exists a regime with $T \geq \mu$, where graphene can be modeled as a dissipative quantum plasma. It is here that insight from holographic models [34] prove to be quite useful.

Recently, experimental evidence for this quantum plasma state has been discovered [19]. Also, some generic electronic models with short-range interactions on the honeycomb lattice, such as the Boson Hubbard Model which models an insulating anti-ferromagnet [72] have been shown to provide examples of quantum critical points without quasiparticle excitations even at $T = 0$.

The aforementioned system, however, is only one example where the physics cannot be explained with quasiparticles. There are many more materials such as the high T_C superconductors, cuprates, in particular, for which we would hope to formulate a working theory. The understanding of the strange metal phase is key as outlined in [Section 2.2](#). The basis of many such ideas formulated today comes from the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev model [41, 63], initially proposed by Sachdev and Ye in 1993[66] to explain the ground states in a random Heisenberg magnet, and was later expanded upon and linked to conformal field theories, by Kitaev in 2015 [41]. It is a concrete starting point to understand these strongly correlated electron systems and will be discussed in detail in the following chapter.

THE SACHDEV-YE-KITAEV MODEL

The interactions between electrons in solids are responsible for a large number of exciting physical phenomena, including ferromagnetism, anti-ferromagnetism and superconductivity. In these materials, we cannot simply treat the electrons as independent entities but have to consider their correlated behaviour.

To engineer a model for such systems, let us start with a set of randomized positions, which are partially filled (with electrons). Now we assume that these electrons are entangled pairwise, arbitrarily. This would imply that, if an electron in the system moves, it would do so in pairs. The new positions will be randomized as well. This motion is in contrast to the one-by-one movement of particles envisioned in the quasiparticle model. Then, every tunneling (movement) generates a non-trivial many-body interaction. Here we can then state that the ground state is then maximally entangled [61]. This serves as the conceptual basis of the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev (SYK) model first proposed by Sachdev and Ye to explain the behaviour of a quantum Heisenberg ferromagnet [66]. It was later adapted and explained by Kitaev in a series of talks [41] as a model for holography with respect to AdS/CFT. Conveniently, the system is solvable in the large N limit which gives us an opportunity to understand more complicated models using the SYK model as a starting point. Also, this serves as a toy model to explain the physics of both strange metals and black holes [34, 63, 71]! Interestingly, this idea isn't new. A similar idea was utilized to study fluctuations in two-body systems involving nuclei[12], but the large N limit was not taken here.

3.1 STRUCTURE OF THE SYK MODEL

The Hamiltonian for the SYK model, based on description written above takes the following form,

$$H_{\text{SYK}} = \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{i,j,k,l=1}^N J_{ij;kl}^c c_i^\dagger c_j^\dagger c_k c_l - \mu \sum_i c_i^\dagger c_i. \quad (3.1)$$

Here, as in Section 2.1.2, c_i^\dagger and c_i represent the fermionic creation and annihilation operators which obey the standard fermion anti-commutation relations

$$c_i c_j + c_j c_i = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad c_i c_j^\dagger + c_j^\dagger c_i = \delta_{ij}, \quad (3.2)$$

which operate on sites $i, j = 1 \dots N$. The physical properties of the model change smoothly with variations in the chemical potential, μ . The chemical potential determines the fermion density

$$Q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_i^\dagger c_i, \quad (3.3)$$

which quantifies the number of lattice sites that are filled with fermions in the SYK model. Importantly, the coupling coefficients $J_{ij;kl}^c$ are independent random variables with

$$\overline{J_{ij;kl}^c} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{|J_{ij;kl}^c|^2} = J^2, \quad (3.4)$$

where J is a constant. N in this Hamiltonian denotes the number of orbitals present within the SYK dot. It is in context to this quantity that a large- N limit is taken. A key property is that in the limit of large N ($N \rightarrow \infty$), this disorder self-averages [17, 63]. In particular, this means that the on-site Green's function is the same independent of site and equal to the disorder-averaged value. The properties described above hold for all $0 < Q < 1$ (respecting Pauli's exclusion principle for fermions). When the large N limit is taken, we can observe critical strange metal behaviour [17, 71].

$$H = \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{i,j,k,\ell=1}^N J_{ij;kl} c_i^\dagger c_j^\dagger c_k c_\ell$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \langle c_i^\dagger c_i \rangle.$$

Figure 3.1: A graphic displaying the interactions within the SYK model. Image taken from [63].

As before (Section 2.1.2) there are 2^N many-body levels, however, these are not all degenerate and hence do not have the same energy E . However, these do

not admit a quasiparticle decomposition ("defining" feature of the SYK analysis). The $T \rightarrow 0$ state has an entropy $S_{GPS} = Ns_0$ with $s_0 = \frac{G}{\pi} + \frac{\ln 2}{4} = 0.464848\dots$ ¹ as calculated by Georges, Parcollet and Sachdev [26, 54] when studying the quantum Heisenberg magnet (G is the Catalan's constant for the half-filled case, $Q = 0$). This means that the spacing near the ground state is of the order e^{-Ns_0} which implies a non-vanishing entropy [25]. This is not expected if quasiparticles existed as highlighted in Section 2.1.2. Hence, we can safely infer that there are no quasiparticles in this model, and the single particle interaction, if considered, would be the only relevant perturbation.

Now, to understand the phenomena that can be realized with the SYK model, it would make sense to extract the equations for the Green's function and the self energy. The Feynman graph expansion in J_{ijkl} and graph-by-graph expansion yields [34, 61, 66] the following exact (self-consistency) equations in the large N limit:

$$G(i\omega) = \frac{1}{i\omega + \mu - \Sigma(i\omega)}, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\Sigma(\tau) = -J^2 G^2(\tau) G(-\tau), \quad (3.6)$$

with an initial condition

$$G(\tau = 0^-) = Q. \quad (3.7)$$

Here, ω is a frequency, and τ denotes imaginary time. These Schwinger Dyson equations can also be derived through the action obtained from the SYK Hamiltonian shown in Eq.(3.1). A derivation for this will be presented in Section 3.2.

It was established by Sachdev and Ye [66] that any solution to these equations must be gapless. To explain this succinctly, the existence of a gap in Eq.(3.5) would imply that G and Σ must have an identical gap, while Eq.(3.6) implies that the gap in Σ should be thrice that of the gap in G . This can be simultaneously true only if the solutions are gapless. The low frequency structure of the Green's function was determined analytically to be:

$$\Sigma(z) = \mu - \frac{1}{A} \sqrt{z} + \dots, \quad (3.8)$$

$$G(z) = \frac{A}{\sqrt{z}}, \quad (3.9)$$

where A is a determinable complex number, and z is the frequency in the upper-half of the complex plane. This results in a ground state that behaves as a non-Fermi liquid since the Green's function in Eq.(3.9) has a branch cut instead of a quasiparticle pole, with a continuously variable density Q . The above

¹ $s_0 < \ln 2$

solution for the Green's Function does not admit the existence of quasiparticle excitations.

In its large N limit, the SYK model is the only known model for systems without quasiparticle excitations that is solvable. Even then, only the low frequency solution is available so far, for $T = 0$ [66] and a finite temperature related to the coupling in the SYK Hamiltonian as $T \ll J_c$. In these solutions, taking the $Q = 1$ limit should lead to the quasiparticle solution.

The solution for the Green's function at $T = 0$ can be written as

$$G(\tau) \sim \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau}} & \tau > 0 \\ \frac{e^{-2\pi\mathcal{E}}}{\sqrt{\tau}} & \tau < 0 \end{cases}. \quad (3.10)$$

Here, \mathcal{E} is a real number related to the phase of the complex number A in Eq.(3.9) [34]. It was shown that \mathcal{E} is a measure of the particle-hole asymmetry in the fermion density of states [26]. That is, if $\mathcal{E} > 0$, the density of states for inserting a particle is larger, and if $\mathcal{E} < 0$, the density of states for inserting a hole is larger. This value of \mathcal{E} can be analytically related to the value of Q via arguments analogous to proving Luttinger's theorem [26].

Additionally, as previously mentioned, it is possible to solve Eq.(3.5) for the Green's function at a small non-zero temperature $T \ll J_c$ [54]. It was found that

$$G_{T \ll J_c}(\tau) \sim \frac{e^{-2\pi\mathcal{E}T\tau}}{\sqrt{\sin(\pi T\tau)}}. \quad (3.11)$$

Interestingly, this form resembles the Green's function of a conformal field theory. Further studies into this, and its reparametrizations can be found in [26, 41].

When calculating the thermal equilibration of the fermion correlators for the above model, we see that $\tau_{eq} \sim \frac{\hbar}{k_B T}$ as $T \rightarrow 0$, and is an example of a strong coupling [24, 54, 66]. This shows us that absence of quasiparticles leads to the fastest possible thermalization (in reaching local equilibrium) and vice-versa. This supports the hypothesis described in Section 2.2, referring to the lower bound proposed by Sachdev[62]). For further information of the role of the SYK model in the study of quantum many body chaos can be found in [17, 63].

3.2 SCHWINGER-DYSON EQUATIONS FOR THE SYK MODEL

To derive the Schwinger-Dyson Equations for the SYK Model, we start with the action of the system. With the Hamiltonian for the model in Eq.(3.1), we can write down the action for such an interaction² (without the potential) as

$$S_{\text{SYK}} = \int d\tau \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{i,j,k,l=1}^N J_{ij;kl}^c c_i^\dagger c_j^\dagger c_k c_l. \quad (3.12)$$

We can now describe a path-integral formulation of the SYK Model. This gives a view of the self-consistency equations as a saddle-point approximation (which becomes exact in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit) to the path integral. The discussion will closely follow the treatment described in detail in previous work on SYK models [17, 66]. The partition function is given by the imaginary-time path integral

$$Z = \int \mathcal{D}c e^{-S_0[c] - S_J[c]}, \quad (3.13)$$

$$S_0[c] = \int d\tau \sum_i c_i^\dagger (\partial_\tau - \mu) c_i, \quad (3.14)$$

$$S_J[c] = \int d\tau \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{ijkl} J_{ij;kl}^c c_i^\dagger c_j^\dagger c_k c_l. \quad (3.15)$$

To handle the SYK interactions, we would have to average over their probability distribution. This should be done using replicas. However, as demonstrated in previous studies of the SYK model [17], due to the self-averaging property of the model, the physical properties that are of interest to physicists can be extracted by simply averaging over a single replica, that is, by directly averaging the partition function. We therefore have to study \bar{Z} . After disorder averaging³, we find

$$\bar{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}c e^{-S_0[c] - S_{\text{int}}[c]}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$S_{\text{int}}[c] = - \frac{J_c^2}{4N^3} \int d\tau d\tau' \left| \sum_i c_i^\dagger(\tau) c_i(\tau') \right|^4. \quad (3.17)$$

Now, let us define the function $G(\tau'; \tau)$ in the following manner,

$$G(\tau'; \tau) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_i^\dagger(\tau') c_i(\tau). \quad (3.18)$$

² Refer to Chapter 4 in [1] for the details of such a computation.

³ Refer to Eq.(3.4) for properties of the interaction.

With this definition in mind, we can insert the following expression, i.e, resolution of identity,

$$1 = \int \mathcal{D}G \delta\left(G(\tau';\tau) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_i^\dagger(\tau) c_i(\tau)\right) \quad (3.19)$$

into the path integral. We then rewrite the delta function as

$$\delta\left(G(\tau';\tau) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_i^\dagger(\tau) c_i(\tau)\right) = \int \mathcal{D}\Sigma e^{\int d\tau d\tau' \Sigma(\tau';\tau) (NG(\tau';\tau) - \sum_i c_i^\dagger(\tau) c_i(\tau))}. \quad (3.20)$$

The disorder averaged interaction can now be expressed directly in terms of G as

$$S_{\text{int}} = -\frac{NJ_c^2}{4} \int d\tau d\tau' |G(\tau';\tau)|^4. \quad (3.21)$$

After these manipulations, the fermion integral is quadratic. Performing this integral, we get

$$\bar{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}G \mathcal{D}\Sigma e^{-NS[G,\Sigma]}, \quad (3.22)$$

$$S[G,\Sigma] = \text{Tr} \ln(\partial_\tau - \mu + \Sigma) - \frac{J_c^2}{4} \int d\tau d\tau' |G(\tau';\tau)|^4 + \int d\tau d\tau' \Sigma(\tau';\tau) G(\tau';\tau). \quad (3.23)$$

We now see that the action has an overall factor of N multiplying it. Thus, in the large- N limit, the integrals for G and Σ can be performed in the saddle-point approximation. It is then easily seen that the saddle-point equations, when taking the derivatives with respect to Σ and G are precisely the self-consistency equations written above,

$$G(\tau) = \frac{1}{\partial_\tau + \mu - \Sigma(\tau)}, \quad (3.24)$$

$$\Sigma(\tau) = -J_c^2 G^2(\tau) G(-\tau). \quad (3.25)$$

The action $S[G,\Sigma]$ then leads to the Luttinger-Ward functional for this model.

The above saddle point equations can also be arrived at through decoupling the interaction terms through two successive Hubbard-Stratonovich transformations (by introducing a real and complex field). This alternate derivation of the Schwinger-Dyson equations can be viewed in [25].

3.3 STRANGE METALS

In [17], Chowdhury et al. proposed solvable models for "Translationally invariant non-Fermi liquid metals with critical Fermi surfaces". A similar strongly correlated metal was built by Song et al. [71]. These models give us an insight into the crossover between the different regimes that occur due to local quantum criticality, as a function of temperature. These were inspired by the properties of the many strongly correlated materials that exhibit a variety of non-Fermi liquid properties, such as the ruthenates, and cuprates among other materials. As described by Chowdhury et al. in their paper [17], some of these materials display a striking non-Fermi liquid behaviour over a large temperature range above an emergent low-energy scale, but develop Fermi-liquid like properties and well-defined Landau quasiparticles below this energy scale. Some of the other materials continue to behave as a non-Fermi liquid down to zero temperature. The most striking example of the above behavior is the strange metal regime [40, 63]. The most interesting property associated with many of these materials is the inverse-linear dependence of the dc conductivity with respect to temperature, without any sign of saturating. In the cuprates, the phenomenology is apparently well described by the marginal-Fermi liquid model [75] mentioned in [Section 2.1.3.1](#).

Broadly speaking, there have been a few proposals to explain the phenomenology of the strange metal phase as listed below.

- A non-Fermi liquid ground state is obtained from coupling a Fermi surface to quantum critical fluctuations of a bosonic degree of freedom. These dominate the properties of the system at temperatures above the critical point [62].
- Electronic fluctuations associated with the destruction of a Fermi surface drive the creation of a class of non-Fermi liquids at quantum critical points. An example of such a non-Fermi liquid is at a Mott transition between a metal and quantum disordered insulator [69].
- Some recent numerical studies of lattice models have found that a non-Fermi liquid can arise as a zero temperature phase, outside of the critical point [37].
- Finally, the strange metal behaviour possibly arises at a limit of considerably strong interactions at an intermediate (non-zero) temperature, without having to tune to the vicinity of a quantum critical point. However, the ground state is typically a Fermi liquid or another well described state, and the strange metal regime appears as a crossover at a high temperature [17, 71]. Only recently, in the aforementioned papers has a theory

of non-Fermi liquids with the linear in T resistivity as a result of strong local interactions been proposed.

There have been many recent experimental realizations of strange metals. As noted in [Section 2.2](#), graphene described at low energies by electronic excitations with a massless Dirac spectrum in 2+1 space-time dimensions with the $\sim \frac{1}{r}$ repulsive Coulomb interaction. It was argued in [\[19, 23\]](#) that the breakdown of screening near the Dirac point should lead to strange metal behavior which can be described by relativistic hydrodynamics in the presence of weak disorder. Similarly with the discovery of high T_C superconductivity [\[6\]](#), studies of the cuprates have found the strongest evidence of the strange metal phase. Further experiments have found the linear in T resistivity as well. In addition, the rare-earth inter-metallic compounds provide realizations of Kondo lattice models, where localized spin moments residing on the rare-earth sites interact with itinerant electrons from the other elements. These provide numerous examples of quantum criticality and strange metal behavior [\[34\]](#).

QUANTUM TRANSPORT

In this chapter, we briefly look at the basic concepts of transport in quantum matter. The discussions in this chapter are adapted from [34, 60, 62].

4.1 TRANSPORT IN SYSTEMS WITH QUASIPARTICLES

Let us start with an overview on transport in metals with quasiparticle excitations. Most of the literature from condensed matter physics detailing quantum transport in metals is based on theories that describe the scattering of quasiparticles in them, formulated using the quantum Boltzmann equation and its Baym-Kadanoff extensions [38, 60].

In the most common and simple cases, elastic scattering off of the impurities in the crystal dominates the scattering of quasiparticles. Typically in this scenario, we are able to define an impurity mean-free path, l_{imp} , and a corresponding impurity scattering time τ_{imp} . These quantities are related through the equation $l_{imp} = v_F \tau_{imp}$, where v_F is the Fermi velocity in the metal. We can assume that the impurity scattering time from elastic scattering is much shorter than the quasiparticle lifetime as a consequence of inelastic processes such as electron-phonon interactions (τ_{ep}) or electron-electron interactions (τ_{ee})

$$\tau_{imp} \ll \tau_{ep}, \tau_{qp:ee}. \quad (4.1)$$

A theory of quasiparticle transport based on the above ideas has a number of well-known characteristics, verified by experimental observations [30]:

- The low temperature resistivity ρ behaves as $\rho = \rho_0 + AT^2$, where ρ_0 is the residual resistivity at zero temperature which arises from impurities, and A is a consequence of the electron-electron interactions which relax momentum in the metal (these often include Umklapp processes).
- The ratio of the electrical conductivity σ , and thermal conductivity κ , obeys the Wiedemann-Franz law

$$\frac{\kappa}{T\sigma} = \frac{\pi^2}{3} \frac{k_B^2}{e^2}$$

- Identifying the existence of a quasiparticle requires a length scale larger than that of the typical wavelength of a quasiparticle excitation $\sim k_F^{-1}$. As a result, the value of l_{imp} is only meaningful when it is larger than k_F^{-1} . The inequality, $k_F l_{imp} > 1$, then leads to the proposal [33] of the Mott-Ioffe-Regel lower bound on the conductivity of a metal

$$\sigma \sim \frac{e^2}{h} k_F^{d-1} l_{imp} > \frac{e^2}{h} k_F^{d-2}.$$

4.1.1 Drude theory of transport

One of the simplest theory of transport in materials is the Drude model [3, 42] of electrical conduction. The model is an application of kinetic theory that assumes that the microscopic behaviour of electrons in a solid may be treated classically. It can be described as a sea of constantly moving electrons bouncing off of heavier, and relative to the electrons, immobile positive ions. In this subsection, we will provide a short version of this theory from a classical perspective.

Some of the base assumptions that Drude [20] made while formulating this models are as follows:

- The interaction of an electron in between collisions is neglected;
- Collisions in the Drude model are instantaneous events that abruptly alter the velocity of an electron;
- Electrons experience a collision with a probability per unit time $1/\tau$, where τ is known as the mean free time;
- Electrons achieve thermal equilibrium with their surroundings only through collisions; and
- In zero field, the average drift velocity $\langle \mathbf{v} \rangle = 0$, but the electrons are not stationary, i.e., $\langle \mathbf{v}^2 \rangle = v^2$.

To start, the current density carried by the electrons in zero electric field is $\mathbf{j} = n(-e)\mathbf{v} = 0$, where n is the number density of electrons. Now applying a constant electric field E , we get the force from Newton's second law $F = m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt}$ that

$$m \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -eE + \frac{m\mathbf{v}}{\tau}, \quad (4.2)$$

where $-eE$ is the force due to the electric field and $\frac{m\mathbf{v}}{\tau}$ is the average force contributed by electrons due to the momentum accumulated between collisions. Now, upon taking the Fourier transform (in frequency space) of this equation:

$$i\omega m v = -eE + \frac{m\mathbf{v}}{\tau}, \quad (4.3)$$

we obtain a solution for the velocity,

$$v(\omega) = \frac{-eE}{m(i\omega - \frac{1}{\tau})}. \quad (4.4)$$

We obtain a result for the conductivity from the current density $\mathbf{j} = en\mathbf{v}$ and taking the $\omega \rightarrow 0$ limit for the conductivity σ , $j = \sigma E$:

$$\sigma(\omega)_{\omega \rightarrow 0} = \frac{ne^2\tau}{m}. \quad (4.5)$$

This is known as the Drude dc conductivity and $\frac{1}{\tau}$ is the scattering. As mentioned in [Section 2.1](#), the scattering rate for Fermi liquid behaves as $\frac{1}{\tau} \sim \frac{T^2}{\epsilon_F}$. From this we can see the behaviour of the resistivity $\rho = \sigma^{-1}$ in a Fermi liquid:

$$\rho = \frac{m}{e^2n\tau} \sim T^2. \quad (4.6)$$

4.2 BREAKDOWN IN TRANSPORT WITH QUASIPARTICLES

We are, however, interested in metals without quasiparticle excitations where the three quasiparticle transport characteristics listed above do not apply. To improve our understanding of the concepts, it is instructive to discuss their break-down in a situation which already manifests within the quasiparticle picture.

Let us consider a metal where τ_{imp} is very long, where the scattering of quasiparticles off of phonons is dominant. This was the situation considered by Bloch in his work [8], in 1929, where he derived "Bloch's law" which can be understood to state that, at low T the resistivity of metals ρ due to electron-phonon scattering varies with temperature as T^{d+2} [7].

However, soon after in 1920, Peierls [56, 57] pointed out a crucial mistake in Bloch's argument. In the case of electron-phonon scattering, the momentum carried by quasiparticles is transferred to the phonons, and the total momentum of the entire electron-phonon system is conserved¹. After multiple scattering events, entire electron-phonon system should reach a state of maximum entropy which is consistent with the conservation of total momentum. In a general state of quantum matter at non-zero density, the momentum-current correlator is non-zero². As a consequence, such an equilibrated state has a non-zero electrical

¹ Umklapp events are frozen out at low temperatures.

² In CFTs, however, this correlator vanishes [34].

current which would be proportional to the initial total momentum. This means that the current does not decay to zero, and the resistivity of metal vanishes³.

It has been seen that Bloch's law explains resistivity in metals quite well. However, Peierl's phonon drag has been difficult to observe. This is a consequence of two factors:

- the electron-phonon coupling is weak, and hence it takes a long time for the electron-phonon system to reach a local thermal equilibrium; and
- impurities are inevitably present in experiments, and they may absorb the momentum deposited to the phonons before the electron-phonon system has reached equilibrium.

We would need metals with exceptional purity and with considerably large electron-phonon (or electron-electron) interactions, to observe the long-lived flow of electrical current in a electronic system at thermal equilibrium. Only recently have such experiments become possible [4, 48].

This gives us insight on reaching a state without quasiparticle excitations. If we increase the strength of electron-electron interactions in a system with quasiparticles, we reduce the value of τ_{ee} . In a moderately clean sample, Eq.(4.1) would be violated before the quasiparticles become ill-defined. As a consequence, the phonon drag mechanism would apply to metals without quasiparticles, and transport should be described in terms of a quantum fluid that has reached local thermal equilibrium. Until recently, many computations of non-Fermi liquid transport [36] used a Boltzmann-Baym-Kadanoff-Keldysh framework to describe the scattering of charged excitations around a Fermi surface by their strong coupling to a neutral bosonic excitation, and then relate this scattering rate to the transport coefficients [34]. These computations, however, do not consider that the bosonic excitations will rapidly approach a state of equilibrium with the charged fermionic excitations in a short time $\tau_{eq} \sim \frac{1}{T}$, as discussed in Section 2.2. This then yields incorrect results for the transport coefficients for the models studied [62]. This is known as the momentum bottleneck.

The holographic perspective on strange metals is advantageous since the momentum bottleneck is a feature of the theory. The description of the transport is independent of the Fermi surface, and does not assume quasiparticles. Another option possible due to non-quasiparticle transport is that momentum may be strongly degraded. This can occur if the effects of disorder or lattice scattering are large. This leads us more likely to enter an incoherent metallic regime. Incoherent metals tend towards a local equilibrium, but the only collective

³ To obtain a non-zero resistivity, a momentum relaxing mechanism is required, i.e., the presence of disorder or umklapp scattering (since electron-electron or electron-phonon scattering conserves momentum).

motion of charge is diffusive. They can have large resistivities, in contrast to the momentum drag transport where the conductivity is large [34]. They are, hence, a suitable idea to describe metals that violate the known characteristics for metals listed in the previous section. The best known quantum matter realization for these incoherent metals is the SYK model, introduced in Chapter 3. These regimes are an example of quantum critical regimes [62], and the basic idea of transport in such a regime in the absence of quasiparticles, is explained in the following section. For further discussion of transport in $d = 2$, stemming from the quasiparticle picture, refer to [62].

4.3 QUANTUM CRITICAL TRANSPORT

To set up our understanding of quantum critical transport⁴, let us consider the simplest case of transport of a conserved charge density $\rho(x, t)$ (with a global $U(1)$ symmetry). Conservation of this quantity implies that there is a current $J_i(x, t)$ (where $i = 1 \dots d$) such that

$$\partial_t \rho + \partial_i J_i = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

What we are interested in here, are the consequences of the above conservation law for non-zero temperatures ($T > 0$) that affect the correlators of ρ and J_i in quantum systems that lack quasiparticle excitations.

We can start with a simple system in $d = 1$: a narrow wire of electrons which form a Luttinger-Tomonaga liquid⁵ [27]. In field theories, such liquids are classified as CFT₂⁶ In literature concerning CFTs, it is conventional to describe correlator functions in terms of holomorphic variables, constructed out of Euclidean space and time τ . The space-time coordinate is expressed in terms of a complex number $z = x + i\tau$, and the density and current are combined to yield a single quantity, the holomorphic current \mathcal{J} . There is a known property of correlators in CFT₂s that

$$\langle \mathcal{J}(z) \mathcal{J}(0) \rangle = \frac{\mathcal{K}}{z^2}, \quad (4.8)$$

where \mathcal{K} is a quantity that can be described as the "level" of conserved current. To make this knowledge useful for us, we would like to rephrase this correlator in terms of more common variables in condensed matter, i.e, the momentum k

⁴ The quantum critical regime is characterized by non-conventional behavior such as the absence of quasiparticles [62, 76].

⁵ For simplicity, the spin of electrons are ignored in this discussion.

⁶ 2D Conformal Field Theory. For an introduction, refer to [68].

and Euclidean frequency ω . By applying a Fourier transform on Eq.(4.8), we obtain⁷

$$\langle |\rho(k, \omega)|^2 \rangle = \mathcal{K} \frac{c^2 k^2}{c^2 k^2 + \omega^2}. \quad (4.9)$$

An interesting property of the above equation is that it can also hold for systems at $T > 0$. As explained in [35], this is a consequence of the conformal mapping between the planar space-time geometry at $T = 0$, and the cylindrical geometry of $T > 0$. This mapping leads to no changes in the Euclidean time correlator from Eq.(4.9) other than the restriction that ω is a Matsubara frequency [1, 16], i.e., ω is an integer multiple of $2\pi T$. By making an analytical continuation from the correlator in Eq.(4.9) through the transformation $i\omega \rightarrow \omega + i\epsilon$, we can obtain the retarded two-point correlator of the density, i.e., the retarded Green's function

$$G_{\rho\rho}^R = \mathcal{K} \frac{c^2 k^2}{c^2 k^2 - (\omega + i\epsilon)^2}, \quad d = 1 \quad (4.10)$$

where ϵ is a positive infinitesimal value. The above equation will hold for all CFT2s with a global $U(1)$ symmetry at any temperature [34].

Now, the above equation is not the expected solution for a generic non-integrable interacting quantum system at $T > 0$, for small ω and k . Upon applying a perturbation that affects the uniformity of the density, we would expect such a system to relax towards an equilibrium state (of maximum entropy). This relaxation occurs through a hydrodynamic diffusion of the conserved density quantity. That is, we can expect that on time scales comparable to $\hbar/k_B T$ (as seen in Section 2.2, we have

$$J_i \approx -D\partial_i\rho + O(\partial^3). \quad (4.11)$$

As described in [39], the assumption that hydrodynamics is an accurate description of the dynamic forces leads to the retarded Green's function being described as

$$G_{\rho\rho}^R = \chi \frac{Dk^2}{Dk^2 - i\omega}. \quad (4.12)$$

Here D is the diffusion constant, and χ is the susceptibility⁸. In terms of thermodynamic quantities, $\chi = \partial\rho/\partial\mu$, where μ is the chemical potential. The Green's function above, can be found by solving the classical diffusion equation using the correct initial conditions. The differences between Eq.(4.10)

⁷ Here, c is the velocity of light in the CFT2 theory

⁸ Sometimes referred to as compressibility coefficient.

and Eq.(4.12) leads us to realize that all such theories have integrable density correlators and that they do not relax towards a thermal equilibrium.

The Green's function from Eq.(4.12) is not quite right in CFT₃s either since it ignores deviations caused by hydrodynamic fluctuations. These are, however, sub-leading effects in these theories and only lead to weaker corrections in higher dimensions [34, 39] and can be ignored for now. For CFT₃s that have translation invariance broken, Eq.(4.12) will hold exactly at low frequencies, as the sub-leading effects will be suppressed by an extra power of ω as $\omega \rightarrow 0$ [21].

Of most interest to us is a theory of an interacting CFT₃, since these are the theories that many quantum phase transitions seem to take the form of⁹ In this case, we have a current J_μ ($\mu = 0, \dots, d$). The conservation and conformal invariance of this quantity imply [61, 62] that at $T = 0$ and in d spatial dimensions:

$$\langle J_\mu(\rho) J_\nu(\rho) \rangle = -\mathcal{K} |k|^{d-1} \left(\delta_{\mu\nu} - \frac{k_\mu k_\nu}{k^2} \right), \quad (4.13)$$

where k is a Euclidean space-time momentum and \mathcal{K} is a dimensionless number characteristic of the CFT¹⁰. The non-analytic power of k here arises from the fact that ρ and J_i have a dimensional scale d . Taking the $\mu = \nu = 0$ component of the currents J_i in the correlator from Eq.(4.13) and making an analytic continuation to obtain the retarded Green's function, we get

$$G_{\rho\rho}^R = \mathcal{K} \frac{k^2}{\sqrt{k^2 - (\omega + i\epsilon)^2}}, \quad d = 2, T = 0. \quad (4.14)$$

Now, despite Eq.(4.14) being an exact result for all CFT₃s, we cannot assume that it will hold for $T > 0$. However, we expect that for $\omega, k \ll T$, these CFT₃s will have like a generic non-integrable quantum system and relax to a thermal equilibrium via diffusion. This means that we, in effect, expect the existence of a crossover in behavior from Eq.(4.14) for $\omega, k \gg T$ to Eq.(4.12) for $\omega, k \ll T$ ¹¹ [34]. Furthermore, utilizing the fact that only the temperature T is a dimensionful parameter in the theory, we can write down the following expressions from dimensional analysis

$$\chi = C_\chi T, \quad D = \frac{C_D}{T}, \quad (4.15)$$

giving us the T dependence of the susceptibility χ and diffusion coefficient D . Here, $C_{\chi, D}$ are dimensionless numbers also characteristic of the CFT₃.

⁹ Examples of which would be the Phase Transitions concerning Dirac Fermions or the Wilson-Fisher fixed point for Superfluid-Insulator transitions.

¹⁰ It is analogous to the \mathcal{K} in Eq.(4.8)

¹¹ At ultralow frequencies, the theory of hydrodynamics breaks down due to long-time tails(sub-leading effects) mentioned before [21].

Most importantly, these expressions yield the conductivity $\sigma(\omega)$ when we apply the Kubo formula¹² [1, 46]:

$$\sigma(\omega) = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow 0} \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \frac{-i\omega}{k^2} G_{\rho\rho}^R(k, \omega). \quad (4.16)$$

In addition, from Eq.(4.14) we can conclude that

$$\sigma(\omega \gg T) = \mathcal{K}, \quad (4.17)$$

and from Eq.(4.12) and Eq.(4.15) we get

$$\sigma(\omega \ll T) = \mathcal{C}_\chi \mathcal{C}_D. \quad (4.18)$$

As seen from the above relationships for σ , we can see that the crossover between the limits is determined by a function of ω/T . It should be noted that the above conductivity is measured in units of e^2/\hbar .

The dc conductivity

$$\sigma = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow 0} \sigma(\omega), \quad (4.19)$$

determines the dissipation due to an arbitrarily low frequency current being driven through the system. It should therefore be obtainable in an effective low energy description of the physics. However, the computation of the remaining coefficients for CFT₃s is not a simple task. Methods detailing these can be seen in [34]. Some of these methods arise from the quasiparticle picture as well. As a reference, an example of complete calculations pertaining to the quantum critical regime in graphene can be found in [23].

¹² The Kubo formula is an equation which expresses the linear response of an observable quantity due to a time-dependent perturbation.

Part II

CALCULATION OF THE CONDUCTIVITY FOR AN HONEYCOMB SYK HYPERLATTICE

In [Part ii](#) of the thesis, we discuss the main body of work. A model that is capable of exhibiting the strange metal regime is constructed using SYK dots on a lattice. The full propagators for such a system are computed. Finally, the dc conductivity for such a model is calculated and two distinct regimes are observed.

HONEYCOMB LATTICE WITH SYK DOTS

From this point on, we are interested in a particular setup of a Honeycomb lattice with each lattice site containing an SYK dot. As mentioned in [Section 2.3](#), graphene, a material described by the honeycomb lattice manifests properties of a system indescribable by models with quasiparticles. Also, when studying such a system, we find that there exists no Fermi surface for the undoped material. Instead, there are Dirac Points at which Dirac cones are formed [[22](#), [50](#)]. The physics of this system, despite being at low-energy, is relativistic. This makes it an interesting lattice for us to study. We seek to understand how the electric transport coefficient behaves in a system engineered with an SYK dot at every honeycomb lattice site. The question whether a crossover regime to a marginal Fermi liquid exists, arises. "How does the conductivity behave in this system?" is also an important question that we hope to address. In this chapter, we will set up the Honeycomb Lattice and calculate the Green's function for the system.

5.1 THE HAMILTONIAN

The honeycomb lattice is well known today, as it has been studied extensively since experiments by Novoselov and Geim [[51](#)] showed us the remarkable properties of graphene. In our setup, we consider a microscopic model with the honeycomb lattice ($d = 2$) where each lattice site is replaced by an SYK dot. Each SYK dot contains N orbitals per site. As in a single SYK dot, we assume there is a global $U(1)$ symmetry that corresponds to a conserved density, Q , which is defined as in [Chapter 3](#). The value of Q can be tuned via the chemical potential μ . We consider hopping between the lattice sites themselves, as well as the SYK interaction. We can then write down the following tight binding Hamiltonian:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} \sum_l (-t_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}^c - \mu_c \delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}) c_{\mathbf{r}l}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}'l} + \frac{1}{(2N)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \sum_r \sum_{ijkl} U_{ijkl}^c c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}j}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}k} c_{\mathbf{r}l}. \quad (5.1)$$

Here, $t_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}^c$ are the hopping parameters between sites \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}' , which are diagonal in the orbital subspace and only dependent on $|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|$. The SYK interaction term is the same as previously show in [Eq.\(3.1\)](#) and described in [Chapter 3](#).

To reiterate, the interaction term U_{ijkl}^c characterizes the strength of the SYK interactions. It is purely on site and obeys the following properties

$$\overline{U_{ijkl}^c} = 0, \quad \overline{(U_{ijkl}^c)^2} = U_c^2, \quad (5.2)$$

and in addition the SYK interaction terms are anti-symmetric:

$$U_{ijkl}^c = -U_{jikl}^c = -U_{ijlk}^c, \quad U_{ijkl}^c = U_{lkij}^c. \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5.1: A two-dimensional honeycomb lattice where each site contains an SYK Dot with N orbitals (represented by different colors). The hoppings t_c are between any neighboring sites. Each site is identical and the system is translationally invariant. The enlarged dot displays the internal structure of a single site with N orbitals with on-site interactions, U_{ijkl}^c .

Following the models constructed by Chowdhury et al. [17], we define our translational invariance by assuming that the coupling constants on different sites have the same distribution, as well as that they are identical to each other. This means that while the interaction strength U_c is a random variable, this variable holds the same value irrespective of the lattice site. With this in mind, Eq.(5.1) is translationally invariant. In addition, $c_{r_i}^\dagger$ and c_{r_l} are the fermionic creation and annihilation operators satisfying

$$c_{r_i} c_{r_j} + c_{r_j} c_{r_i} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad c_{r_i} c_{r'_j}^\dagger + c_{r'_j}^\dagger c_{r_i} = \delta_{ij} \delta_{r r'}. \quad (5.4)$$

It should be noted that there are two distinct parts of the Hamiltonian from Eq.(5.1). There is the SYK Interaction term \mathcal{H}_{SYK} as described by Eq. (3.1) as well as the remaining contributions \mathcal{H}_0 , which characterize the hopping between nearest lattice sites.

5.2 DESCRIPTION OF HONEYCOMB LATTICE

Before considering the SYK interactions, it would be pertinent to understand the system considering the hopping between lattice sites. For this the geometry of the lattice is important. The hopping-only Hamiltonian is

$$\mathcal{H}_0 = \sum_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'} \sum_l (-t_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}^c - \mu_c \delta_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}) c_{\mathbf{r}l}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}'l}. \quad (5.5)$$

Figure 5.2: An illustration of a honeycomb lattice [50]

The lattice vectors for the honeycomb lattice can be written as

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = a \left(\frac{3}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right), \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = a \left(\frac{3}{2}, -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right), \quad (5.6)$$

where a is the lattice spacing constant. From this we obtain the reciprocal lattice vectors¹

$$\mathbf{b}_1 = b \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{3}{2} \right), \quad \mathbf{b}_2 = b \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, -\frac{3}{2} \right), \quad (5.7)$$

where b is the reciprocal lattice vector spacing and $b = \frac{4\pi}{3\sqrt{3}a}$. The reciprocal lattice also takes the form of a honeycomb lattice.

In real space, from any lattice site considered as the origin $(0,0)$, translational hopping takes place along the following vectors δ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$)

$$\delta_1 = a (1, 0), \quad (5.8)$$

$$\delta_2 = a \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right), \quad (5.9)$$

$$\delta_3 = a \left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \right). \quad (5.10)$$

¹ In a 2D Bravais lattice, if $\mathbf{R}_n = n_1 \mathbf{a}_1 + n_2 \mathbf{a}_2$ in real space and $\mathbf{G}_m = m_1 \mathbf{b}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{b}_2$ in reciprocal space, $\mathbf{G}_m \mathbf{R}_n = 2\pi N$, where $N \in \mathbb{Z}$.

We can then identify the Dirac points that form in this lattice:

$$\mathbf{K} = b \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (5.11)$$

$$\mathbf{K}' = b \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, -\frac{1}{2} \right). \quad (5.12)$$

As seen above, there are two distinct lattice sites A and B in the honeycomb lattice. Since only nearest-neighbor hopping is included in our model, $t_{\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}'}$ would imply hopping between a lattice site of type A to a lattice site of type B and vice-versa. Considering the fermionic operators to be dependent on the site, we now rewrite the Hamiltonian Eq.(5.5) in the following matrix form

$$\mathcal{H}_0 = \sum \sum \begin{pmatrix} c_A^\dagger & c_B^\dagger \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Delta(k) \\ \Delta^*(k) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_A \\ c_B \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.13)$$

where $\Delta(k) = -tf(k)$. $f(k)^2$ is the sum over \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}' for the hopping term which is equal to

$$f(k) = \sum_{\delta_i} e^{ik\delta_i} = e^{ik_x a} + 2e^{-\frac{1}{2}ik_x a} \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}k_y a\right). \quad (5.14)$$

Now, diagonalizing the Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_0 , we get

$$\mathcal{H}_0 = \sum \sum \begin{pmatrix} c_A^\dagger & c_B^\dagger \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{k_+} & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_{k_-} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_A \\ c_B \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.15)$$

where the eigenvalues are $\varepsilon_{k_\pm} = \pm \Delta(k)$.

The physics of the system of most interest to us takes place in the vicinity of the Dirac points. We then find the dispersion around the Dirac points, which allows us to consequently obtain an expression for the Green's function. First, around the Dirac point, define the vector $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{K}$. Now, approximating the function $tf(k)$ around the Dirac point, i.e., making a Taylor expansion around $\mathbf{q} = 0$ we obtain

$$tf(k)|_{\mathbf{q}=0} \simeq 2te^{-ik_x a} \mathbf{q} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{k}} \left(e^{\frac{3}{2}ik_x a} \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}k_y a\right) \right) \Big|_{\mathbf{k}=\mathbf{K}} \quad (5.16)$$

$$= -\frac{3ta}{2} e^{-ik_x a} (q_x - iq_y) \quad (5.17)$$

Now, after switching $\mathbf{q} \rightarrow \mathbf{k}$ to ensure consistent notation through the calculations, we have

$$\Delta(k) = \hbar v_F (k_x + ik_y) \left\{ 1 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{k}{K}\right)^2 \right\}, \quad (5.18)$$

$$\Delta^*(k) \approx \hbar v_F (k_x - ik_y), \quad (5.19)$$

where v_F is Fermi velocity and $v_F = \frac{3ta}{2\hbar}$.

$$2|f(k)| = \sqrt{3 + 2\cos(\sqrt{3}k_y a) + 4\cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}k_y a\right)\cos\left(\frac{3}{2}k_x a\right)}$$

Figure 5.3: Dispersion of a honeycomb lattice, where the Dirac cones can be seen as the point where the two bands meet.

5.3 PROPAGATOR WITHIN THE HONEYCOMB LATTICE

For a larger discussion of the concepts used in this subsection, refer to any of the following books [1, 16, 46, 47]. In addition, [53] has a well written pedagogical approach to Green's functions. In condensed matter systems, the Green's function is a powerful tool in allowing us to study the evolution of systems over a period of time, which is why the Green's function is alternatively known as the propagator. For a linear operator \mathcal{L} , the Green's function $G(x, s)$ is defined through the following expression

$$\mathcal{L}G(x, s) = \delta(x - s). \quad (5.20)$$

For any quantum mechanical model that obeys the time-dependent Schrödinger's equation [70]

$$i\partial_t|\Psi\rangle = (\hat{H}_0 + \hat{V})|\Psi\rangle, \quad (5.21)$$

we can write a linear operator $\mathcal{L} = [i\partial_t - H_0 - V]$, such that we obtain the Green's function through

$$\begin{aligned} [i\partial_t - H_0 - V]G(r, t, r', t') &= \delta(r - r')\delta(t - t'), \\ \Rightarrow G^{-1} &= i\partial_t - H_0 - V. \end{aligned} \quad (5.22)$$

$G(r, t, r', t')$ is known as the full propagator or Green's function. We can define the bare propagator as the Green's function that does not take into account interactions (the potential V) through

$$G_0^{-1} = i\partial_t - H_0, \quad (5.23)$$

which upon taking the Fourier transform takes the form

$$G_0^{-1}(k) = i\omega_k - \varepsilon_k. \quad (5.24)$$

Since the matrices in Eq.(5.13) and Eq.(5.15) are equal, we finally arrive at the bare Green's function for the system on the honeycomb lattice:

$$G_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} i\omega_k & -\Delta_k \\ -\Delta_k^* & i\omega_k \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.25)$$

Taking into account that we are interested in the physics in the vicinity of the Dirac point K , we use Eq.(5.18) to get the version of the bare propagator that will be used in the following chapters:

$$G_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} i\omega_k & -k_x - ik_y \\ -k_x + ik_y & i\omega_k \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.26)$$

$$\Rightarrow G_0 = \frac{-1}{\omega^2 + k^2} \begin{pmatrix} i\omega_k & k_x + ik_y \\ k_x - ik_y & i\omega_k \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.27)$$

In contrast, the Green's function in proximity to the other Dirac point K'

$$G'_0 = \frac{-1}{\omega^2 + k^2} \begin{pmatrix} i\omega_k & k_x - ik_y \\ k_x + ik_y & i\omega_k \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.28)$$

5.4 GREEN'S FUNCTION FOR THE SYK MODEL

In the previous section, we arrived at the bare Green's function for the honeycomb lattice Eq.(5.26). However, as can be noticed this propagator does not take into account the SYK interactions. We cannot simply introduce the interaction into the bare propagator to obtain the full (or dressed) propagator. Instead we anticipate a crossover in behavior between the physics described by a regime where intra-lattice hopping dominates, and one where there the interaction within the SYK dot is dominant. Using the solutions to the Green's function as in Eq.(3.10) (derived in [66]) as a template, we use the following ansatz for the bare Green's function for the SYK interaction in frequency space,

$$G_c(\omega) \sim \frac{i \operatorname{sgn}(\omega)}{\sqrt{U_c \omega}}. \quad (5.29)$$

This ansatz is momentum-independent, as expected since a single SYK quantum dot is (0+1) dimensional. The Green's function does not depend on the position of the dot, and only the time evolution contributes. In addition, as mentioned in the above paragraph, we anticipate a crossover dependent on the energy (temperature) scale. We label this crossover energy as Ω_c^* throughout the calculation.

FULL PROPAGATOR FOR HONEYCOMB SYK LATTICE

In order to gain a better understanding of transport in our model, it would be pertinent to compute the full propagator. With the knowledge of the bare Green's function, this can be done using the Dyson Equation [1, 16, 46]:

$$G = G_0 + G_0 \Sigma G, \quad (6.1)$$

a self-consistent equation which leads to the following expression for the full propagator

$$G_{ij}^{-1} = G_{0ij}^{-1} - \Sigma_{ij}. \quad (6.2)$$

Figure 6.1: Feynman graph representation of the Dyson Equation. Single lines represent the bare propagator G_0 , double lines represent the full propagator G , and the vertex represents the self energy Σ .

This of course leads us to compute the self energy Σ first. To do so, we utilize the self-consistent Schwinger-Dyson equations derived in Section 3.2. Despite being derived for a single SYK dot, these equations still hold for a lattice of SYK dots. This is shown in Appendix A. The expanded version of the Schwinger Dyson equations are shown below:

$$G_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{1}{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}} - \Sigma_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega)}, \quad (6.3)$$

$$\Sigma_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = -U_c^2 \iiint_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}} G_c(\mathbf{q}, i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}) G_c(\mathbf{p}, i\omega_{\mathbf{p}}) G_c(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + i\omega_{\mathbf{p}} - i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}), \quad (6.4)$$

where the integral is expanded as $\int_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv \int d^d \mathbf{k} (2\pi)^{-d}$.

As mentioned previously, these equations correspond to the resummation of an infinite class of "watermelon diagrams". For the ease of computation in

Figure 6.2: Feynman graph representation of the watermelon diagram for the self energy Σ . Each solid black line represents the full Green's function G and the dashed line represents a contraction of value U_c^2 and carries no frequency or momentum.

certain situations, we can also split the above two equations, into a set of three self-consistent equations:

$$G_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{1}{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}} - \Sigma_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega)}, \quad (6.5)$$

$$\Sigma_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = -U_c^2 \iint_{\mathbf{q}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}} G_c(\mathbf{q}, i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}) \Pi_c(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} + i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}), \quad (6.6)$$

$$\Pi_c(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \iint_{\mathbf{q}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}} G_c(\mathbf{q}, i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}) G_c(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} + i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}), \quad (6.7)$$

where we introduce the polarization of the system Π . Π corresponds to the following diagram.

Figure 6.3: Feynman graph representation of the polarization bubble $\Pi_{\mathbf{k}}$. Each single line represents the bare propagator G_0 .

We start with the ansatz' bare Green's function G_0 :

$$G_0(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \begin{cases} \frac{-1}{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + k^2} \begin{pmatrix} i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} & k_x + ik_y \\ k_x - ik_y & i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix} & \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < \Omega_c^* \\ \frac{i\text{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{U_c \omega_{\mathbf{k}}}} & \Omega_c^* < \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < U_c \end{cases}. \quad (6.8)$$

Since there are two different regimes there are likely to be two separate regimes for the self energy as well and their computation must be done individually as seen in the next section. It should be noted that the ansatz for the full Green's function in the regime $\omega_{\mathbf{k}} < \Omega_c^*$ is of the form:

$$G(\mathbf{k}, i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{-1}{Z^{-2}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + k^2} \begin{pmatrix} iZ^{-1}\omega_{\mathbf{k}} & k_x + ik_y \\ k_x - ik_y & iZ^{-1}\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix} \quad \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < \Omega_c^* \quad (6.9)$$

6.1 CALCULATION OF THE SELF ENERGY - BELOW CROSSOVER SCALE

6.1.1 Diagonal terms of the self energy matrix

Here, we will first compute the non-self-consistent solution for the self energy¹ Σ_0 using the bare Green's function G_0 in the diagrams, instead of the full Green's function G . The self-consistent solution that we require only changes the computed solution slightly as we will see, through a prefactor to the frequency dependent term. We start with the calculation for the self energy by utilizing the Fourier transformed version of the self-consistency equations,

$$\Sigma_{rr'} = U_c^2 G_{rr'}^2(\tau) G_{r'r}(-\tau) \xrightarrow{FT} \Sigma_k^{\alpha\beta} G_q^{\alpha\beta} G_p^{\alpha\beta} G_{q+p-k}^{\beta\alpha}. \quad (6.10)$$

We also solve for the different components of the self energy separately for ease of calculation. Since $G_0^{11} = G_0^{22}$, their respective self energies will also be the same $\Sigma_0^{11} = \Sigma_0^{22}$. Substituting this ansatz into the above equation, we get

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22}(k) = -2U_c^2 \iint_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}} \frac{i\omega_{\mathbf{q}}}{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + \mathbf{q}^2} \cdot \frac{i\omega_{\mathbf{p}}}{\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + \mathbf{p}^2} \cdot \frac{i(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})^2 + (\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2}. \quad (6.11)$$

¹ The self-consistent self energy Σ is obtained using the full Green's function.

The factor 2 in this expression takes into account a contribution from electrons in the bubble at the other Dirac point. Using the Feynman parametrization technique (Section B.1) where we are able to rewrite the product of denominators in the following manner

$$\frac{1}{A_1 A_2 A_3} = 2 \int_0^1 \frac{\delta(1-x-y-z)}{(xA_1 + yA_2 + zA_3)^3} dx dy dz, \quad (6.12)$$

we can simplify Eq.(6.11). This leads to

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22} = -2U_c^2 \iiint_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, x, y, z} \frac{\delta(1-x-y-z) \cdot (-i) \cdot \omega_{\mathbf{q}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}} (\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x\mathbf{q}^2 + y\mathbf{p}^2 + z(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2 \\ + x\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + y\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + z(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})^2 \end{array} \right\}^3}. \quad (6.13)$$

This denominator can be simplified further² to obtain

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22} = -2U_c^2 \iiint_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, x, y, z} \frac{\delta(1-x-y-z) \cdot (-i) \cdot \omega_{\mathbf{q}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}} (\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (x+z)\mathbf{q}^2 + \frac{xy+yz+zx}{x+z}\mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{xyz}{xy+yz+zx}\mathbf{k}^2 \\ + x\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + y\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + z(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})^2 \end{array} \right\}^3}, \quad (6.14)$$

with the following substitutions

$$\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q} + \frac{z}{x+z}(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}); \quad \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p} - \frac{xz}{xz + xy + yz}\mathbf{k}. \quad (6.15)$$

Utilizing the following integral [29],

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty dq dp \frac{qp}{[aq^2 + bp^2 + ck^2 + d]^3} = \frac{1}{8ab(ck^2 + d)}, \quad (6.16)$$

we can integrate out the momentum variables \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} . We then have the following frequency-dependent integral for $\Sigma_0^{11/22}$

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22} = \frac{iU_c^2}{4(2\pi)^4} \iiint_{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, x, y, z} \frac{\delta(1-x-y-z) \cdot \omega_{\mathbf{q}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}} (\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{xyz\mathbf{k}^2 + (xy + yz + zx)(x\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + y\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + z(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})^2)}, \quad (6.17)$$

where we next need to integrate over the frequencies $\omega_{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\omega_{\mathbf{p}}$. By identifying that the denominator in Eq.(6.17) with respect to the frequency variables has

² For details of calculation, refer to Section B.2.

a similar form to that of the equation Eq.(6.13) (in terms of the momentum variables), we can perform a near identical transformation to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0^{11/22} = & \frac{iU_c^2}{4(2\pi)^4} \iint_{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, x, y, z} [\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{z}{x+z}(\omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{xy+yz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) - \frac{xy+yz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}] \\ & \cdot \frac{[\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \frac{z}{x+z}(\omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{xy+yz}{xz+yz+xy}\omega_{\mathbf{k}})][\omega_{\mathbf{p}} + \frac{xz}{xz+yz+xy}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}] \delta(1-x-y-z)}{xyz\mathbf{k}^2 + (xy+xz+yz)[(x+z)\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + \frac{xy+xz+yz}{x+z}\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + \frac{xyz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2]}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.18)$$

Despite being a seemingly large and cumbersome integral, we can simplify Eq.(6.18) by making the observation that the denominator is an even function of $\omega_{\mathbf{p}}$ and $\omega_{\mathbf{q}}$. This means that the contributions of the odd powers of $\omega_{\mathbf{p}}$ and $\omega_{\mathbf{q}}$ would vanish while taking the integral over the entirety of the frequency space. This reduces the possible contributions in the numerator of Eq.(6.18) to the sum of the following three terms

$$\frac{xz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2\omega_{\mathbf{k}} + \frac{2xyz - \frac{x^2z^2}{x+z}}{(x+z)(xy+yz+zx)}\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \frac{x^2y^2z^2}{(xy+yz+zx)^3}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^3. \quad (6.19)$$

We are now left to evaluate the following integral

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0^{11/22} = & \frac{iU_c^2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}{4(2\pi)^4} \iint_{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, x, y, z} \frac{\frac{xz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + \frac{2xyz(x+z) - x^2z^2}{(x+z)^2(xy+yz+zx)}\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 - \frac{x^2y^2z^2}{(xy+yz+zx)^3}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2}{(xy+xz+yz)[(x+z)\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + \frac{xy+xz+yz}{x+z}\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + \frac{xyz}{xy+yz+zx}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2]} \\ & \cdot \delta(1-x-y-z) \end{aligned} \quad (6.20)$$

However, this integral is divergent when evaluated over the entirety of the frequency space. We then integrate till the cut-off Ω_c^{*3} to obtain

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22} = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \delta(1-x-y-z) \frac{xz}{(xz+xy+zy)^2} \cdot \frac{2iU_c^2\Omega_c^{*2}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}{(2\pi)^4} dx dy dz. \quad (6.21)$$

Now, performing the integrals over the introduced variables x , y , and z , we get the diagonal terms for the self-energy matrix

$$\Sigma_0^{11/22} = \frac{2iU_c^2}{(2\pi)^4} \cdot \Omega_c^{*2} \cdot \omega_{\mathbf{k}}. \quad (6.22)$$

3 anticipated crossover point

6.1.2 Off-Diagonal terms of the self energy matrix

To complete the construction of the self energy matrix, we need to compute the off-diagonal elements. Starting with the off-diagonal elements of the Green's function from Eq.(6.8) and introducing them to the Schwinger Dyson equations Eq.(6.3) we get

$$\Sigma_0^{12/21} = -2U_c^2 \iint_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \omega_{\mathbf{p}}} \frac{q_x \pm q_y}{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}^2 + \mathbf{q}^2} \cdot \frac{p_x \pm p_y}{\omega_{\mathbf{p}}^2 + \mathbf{p}^2} \cdot \frac{(q_x + p_x - k_x) \pm (q_y + p_y - k_y)}{(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} + \omega_{\mathbf{p}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})^2 + (\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2}. \quad (6.23)$$

While we can solve the above equation for $\Sigma_0^{12/21}$ it is not necessary. We are interested in solving for the full propagator G and we are interested in the self energy, purely for its utility in the Dyson Equation. We can circumvent solving the above equation by simply identifying how the self energy renormalizes the Green's function. To do this, we can approximate the self energy through the means of a Taylor expansion. If we are able to determine the dependence of the first derivatives of the self energy $\Sigma_0^{12/21}$ with respect to the momentum coordinates k_x and k_y , we will be able to see the impact of the said terms on the Green's function. Switching to polar coordinates for the momenta \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} , and taking the partial derivative with respect to k_x (Section B.3), we have

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Sigma_0^{12/21}}{\partial k_x} \right|_{k_x=0} = 0. \quad (6.24)$$

Similarly, we also obtain for k_y that

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Sigma_0^{12/21}}{\partial k_y} \right|_{k_y=0} = 0. \quad (6.25)$$

This tells us that the momentum dependent terms in the full Green's function are not renormalized and as a result $G^{12/21} = G_0^{12/21}$. To obtain the full Green's function, we now utilize the Dyson Equation Eq.(6.2) and our result from Eq.(6.22) to get

$$G_{11/22}^{-1} = i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \frac{2iU_c^2}{(2\pi)^4} \cdot \Omega_c^{*2} \cdot \omega_{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (6.26)$$

$$= i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \left[1 - \frac{2U_c^2 \cdot \Omega_c^{*2}}{(2\pi)^4} \right] = iZ^{-1}\omega_{\mathbf{k}}. \quad (6.27)$$

Here, Z is a renormalizing variable, that we call the quasiparticle residue which was introduced as a self-consistency factor in the ansatz for the full

Green's function in Eq.(6.9). Z provides us with a measure of the presence of quasiparticles in the system. Here we identify that $Z^{-1} = 1 - \kappa$, where $\kappa = \frac{2U_c^2 \cdot \Omega_c^2}{(2\pi)^4}$. For a completely weakly interacting system, the self energy obeys the following condition, $\Sigma = 0$. In this case, the quasiparticle residue Z must be equal to 1.

At this point, we see from the non-self-consistent solution above that Σ_0 only leads to a renormalization of the frequency dependent term in G_0 by the way of a prefactor. The lack of momentum renormalization is shown in Eq.(6.24) and Eq.(6.25). We use this knowledge to confirm the ansatz for G . We require the self-consistent solution for the self energy Σ , which can be calculated using the full propagator ansatz Eq.(6.9), where Z^{-1} was introduced to modify the ansatz for the bare propagator seen in Eq.(6.8). Extending from the non-self-consistent self energy calculation above, we anticipate that the self-consistent self energy Σ only renormalizes the frequency dependent term in G . If we compare the self-consistent self energy Σ obtained from repeating the above calculation after introducing Z^{-1} in the ansatz for G as in Eq.(6.9), with the non-self-consistent self energy Σ_0 , we obtain the following relationship between the self-consistent and non-self-consistent solutions:

$$\Sigma(\omega) = Z^2 \Sigma_0(Z^{-1}\omega). \quad (6.28)$$

With this relationship, we should be able to calculate the self-consistent full propagator G , if we solve for the quasiparticle residue Z . To obtain a solution for Z and hence G , we utilize the Dyson Equation along with the above relationship leading to the following quadratic equation for the quasiparticle residue:

$$Z^{-1} = 1 - \kappa Z, \quad (6.29)$$

$$\kappa Z^2 - Z + 1 = 0, \quad (6.30)$$

$$\implies Z = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{1 - 4\kappa}}{2\kappa}. \quad (6.31)$$

Here, only the solution $Z = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - 4\kappa}}{2\kappa}$ is relevant, since it satisfies the necessary condition imposed by quasiparticle behaviour that $Z = 1$, when $\Sigma = 0$.

Piecing everything together from Eq.(6.24), Eq.(6.25), and Eq.(6.27), we have

$$G^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} iZ^{-1}\omega_{\mathbf{k}} & -k_x - ik_y \\ -k_x + ik_y & iZ^{-1}\omega_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6.32)$$

where $Z = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - 4\kappa}}{2\kappa}$ are the only acceptable solutions for the quasiparticle residue determined from the quadratic equation above. It should be noted that the off-diagonal terms remain the same irrespective of the regime, since the functions describing the aforementioned terms are independent of frequency and do not differ in either region. The terms are reflective of the nature of the Fermi Surface of the Lattice, or in this case the Dirac Points.

6.2 SELF ENERGY ABOVE THE CROSSOVER SCALE

6.2.1 Computation of the polarization bubble

For temperatures above the crossover scale, we have made the assumption that the interaction within the SYK quantum dot dominates the intra-lattice hopping. We then use our ansatz from Eq.(6.8):

$$G(i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{-i \operatorname{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{U_c |\omega_{\mathbf{k}}|}} \quad (6.33)$$

to compute the self energy for this scenario. From our discussion on the SYK Model in [Chapter 3](#), we have an expected solution to the self energy and need to verify whether we reach the same result.

In these computations, we use the form of the Schwinger Dyson equations from Eq.(6.5) instead of from Eq.(6.3) as we used in the previous case. This boils down to convenience and the simpler form that the equations take due to the former situation. Then, the polarization $\Pi_{\mathbf{k}}$ is first computed.

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{\mathbf{k}} &= -\frac{1}{U_c} \int_{\Omega_c^*}^{U_c} \frac{\operatorname{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) \cdot \operatorname{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{q}} (|\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}|)}} d\omega_{\mathbf{q}} \\ &= -\frac{1}{U_c} \left[\left[\log \sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}} + \sqrt{|\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}|} \right] \Big|_{\Omega_c^*}^{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left[\log \sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}} + \sqrt{|\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}|} \right] \Big|_{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}^{U_c} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6.34)$$

Here, depending on the relationship between the frequency $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ and crossover scale Ω_c^* we are left with the following solution to $\Pi_{\mathbf{k}}$.

$$\Pi_{\mathbf{k}} \sim \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{U_c} \log \frac{U_c}{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}, & \omega_{\mathbf{k}} > \Omega_c^* \\ -\frac{1}{U_c} \log \frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*}, & \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < \Omega_c^* \end{cases}. \quad (6.35)$$

We now have the solution to the Polarization bubble in two regimes. However, since the regime we are interested in, is the former, and we have already computed the latter solution in the previous section, we can safely discard the solution to $\Pi_{\mathbf{k}}$ in the regime $\omega_{\mathbf{k}} < \Omega_c^*$. Notice that this solution is constant and only acts as a lower bound to our calculation. This gives us further reason to trust the assumption that intra-lattice hopping is more dominant than the SYK interaction below the crossover scale.

6.2.2 Computation of self energy

Now that we have computed the polarization $\Pi_{\mathbf{k}}$, we can proceed to calculate the self energy using Eq.(6.5). The details of the calculation are left to the appendices (Section B.4). Now, integrating over the product of Eq.(6.33) and Eq.(6.35), we have

$$\Sigma_0 = \int_{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}} \frac{i}{U_c} \log \left[\frac{U_c}{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}} \right] \cdot \frac{U_c^2 \cdot \text{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{U_c} |\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}|}. \quad (6.36)$$

We integrate over $\omega_{\mathbf{q}}$ from the crossover temperature Ω_c^* . However, since this integral is divergent we take a higher cutoff to be at U_c , i.e., at the order of the SYK interaction strength. We then have

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0 = 2i\sqrt{U_c} & \left(2\sqrt{U_c - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}} - 2\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \Omega_c^*} - \sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \Omega_c^*} \left[\log \frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*} \right] \right. \\ & \left. + 2\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \left[\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}} - \Omega_c^*}}{\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}} \right) - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{U_c - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}}}{\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}} \right) \right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (6.37)$$

We can simplify this further by using the relevant Taylor series expansions for $\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{\pm[1-x]})$ around suitable points, since $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ is restricted to the region $\Omega_c^* \ll \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < U_c$. The equation for Σ then simplifies to

$$\Sigma_0 = 4i\sqrt{U_c\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \left[\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{4\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} - \left(1 - \log \left(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \left[1 - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \right] \right] + \mathcal{O}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{-2}) \quad (6.38)$$

We can approximate this further by neglecting the lower order terms of $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, since we are in the high frequency limit. We then have the following relationship for the self energy,

$$\Sigma_0 = 4i\sqrt{U_c\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \left[\frac{\pi}{4} - \left(1 - \log \left(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right]. \quad (6.39)$$

The above result is consistent with the available literature [26, 66] and is of the form we expect from the self energy of the SYK model.

With the above result for the self energy, Eq.(6.39), we obtain the final form for the full propagator using the Dyson Equation, $G^{-1} = G_0^{-1} - \Sigma$:

$$\begin{aligned} G^{-1} &= -i\sqrt{U_c}\sqrt{\omega} - i\alpha\sqrt{U_c}\sqrt{\omega}, \\ &= i\sqrt{U_c}(1 - \alpha)\sqrt{\omega}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.40)$$

where $\alpha = 4 \left[\frac{\pi}{4} - \left(1 - \log \left(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \right]$

In this chapter, we have computed the self energy, and thereby the full propagators of the constructed lattice model described in [Chapter 5](#). It can be seen that irrespective of the regime, the self energy is momentum independent and depends on a singular frequency. The momentum does not contribute to the renormalization of the Green's function, and the full Green's function in both regimes behaves similarly to the bare propagator, albeit multiplied with numerical factor $O(1)$. The full Green's function in both regimes are listed below:

$$G(\mathbf{k}, i\omega) = \begin{cases} \frac{-1}{\omega^2 + k^2} \begin{pmatrix} iZ^{-1}\omega & k_x + ik_y \\ k_x - ik_y & iZ^{-1}\omega \end{pmatrix}, & \omega \ll \Omega_c^* \\ \frac{i\text{sgn}(\omega)}{(1-\alpha)\sqrt{U_c\omega}}, & \omega \gg \Omega_c^* \end{cases}, \quad (6.41)$$

where $Z = \frac{1-\sqrt{1-4\kappa}}{2\kappa}$ is the quasiparticle residue ($\kappa = \frac{U_c^2 \cdot \Omega_c^{*2}}{(2\pi)^4}$), and $\alpha = 4[\frac{\pi}{4} - (1 - \log(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*})^{\frac{1}{2}})]$ is a numerical factor. It is with the above equation that we proceed to calculate the dc conductivity in [Chapter 7](#).

CALCULATION OF THE ELECTRICAL TRANSPORT COEFFICIENT

In the previous chapter, we found a result for the full Green's function. Now, using the ideas discussed in [Chapter 4](#), we can compute the conductivity in the constructed system. This will allow us to verify whether there exists a change in transport behaviour around the crossover scale. Below the crossover scale, since the system admits quasiparticles, we use methods such as those outlined in [\[1, 16, 60\]](#). In the following chapter, the calculations have been performed with the definitions $e = 1$ and $\hbar = 1$.

7.1 CONDUCTIVITY BELOW THE CROSSOVER SCALE

7.1.1 Computation of the current-current correlator

To extract the dc conductivity, $\sigma(\omega)$, we first need to compute the current-current correlator $K_{\mu\nu}$. To do this, we rely on methods used in quantum field theory [\[58, 77\]](#). These quasiparticle methods have also been used to compute transport in the quantum critical regime [\[34\]](#).

We represent the full Green's function from [Eq.\(6.41\)](#) belonging to the regime where $\omega \ll \Omega_c^*$ in the following manner:

$$G(k, \omega) = \langle \psi(k, \omega) \bar{\psi}(k, \omega) \rangle \sim \frac{iZ^{-1}\omega + k_x\tau^y + k_y\tau^x}{Z^{-2}\omega^2 + k_x^2 + k_y^2}, \quad (7.1)$$

where τ^x and τ^y are Pauli matrices. The current in the system is defined as $J_\mu = -i\bar{\psi}\gamma_\mu\psi$, where γ_μ represent the gamma matrices¹ [\[58\]](#). With the current defined, the expression to describe the current-current correlator is simply $K_{\mu\nu} = \langle J_\mu J_\nu \rangle$. Expanded, this becomes

$$K_{\mu\nu} = \langle J_\mu J_\nu \rangle = (-1) \langle \bar{\psi}\gamma_\mu\psi\bar{\psi}\gamma_\nu\psi \rangle. \quad (7.2)$$

The factor (-1) is introduced due to the closure of a fermionic loop [\[58\]](#).

Performing a Wick contraction on the above expression gives us

$$K_{\mu\nu} = \text{Tr}[\gamma_\mu G(k, \omega) \gamma_\nu G(k, \omega)]. \quad (7.3)$$

¹ The gamma matrices used can be found in [\[22\]](#).

Figure 7.1: Diagram of the current-current correlator $K_{\mu\nu}$.

From this point on, for the convenience of calculating we express the Green's function $G(q, \omega)$ as $G(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{\not{q} + m}{q^2 - m^2}$. For reference, this notation is consistent with the standard texts in quantum field theory [58, 77]. We can now expand the current-current correlator to compute it as

$$K_{\mu\nu} = - \int Z \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \text{Tr}[\gamma_\mu G(k+q) \gamma_\nu G(q)], \quad (7.4)$$

$$= -Z \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{\text{Tr}[\gamma_\mu (\not{k} + \not{q} + m) \gamma_\nu (\not{q} + m)]}{[(k+q)^2 - m^2][q^2 - m^2]}, \quad (7.5)$$

where the quasiparticle factor Z arises from the integration measure due to the change in variables. At this point, we use some known properties of the current and current-current correlator to make a structured ansatz for the latter quantity. The current is a conserved quantity, i.e., it satisfies a continuity equation $\partial_\mu J^\mu = 0$ cf. [77], which means that we can derive the following condition on the current-current correlator

$$k^\mu K_{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad (7.6)$$

as shown in Section C.1, which is known as the Ward identity [77]. In addition, under the necessary conditions that $K_{\mu\nu}$ should be covariant as well as gauge invariant [2, 58], we can make the following ansatz for the quantity:

$$K_{\mu\nu}(k) = -Z(k^2 g_{\mu\nu} - k_\mu k_\nu) \Pi(k^2). \quad (7.7)$$

To find an expression for $\Pi(k^2)$, we use the above expression for the quantity K_μ^μ . Since $g_\mu^\mu = d$, where d is the dimension of the system, we have

$$K_\mu^\mu(k) = -Z(k^2 g_\mu^\mu - k^\mu k_\mu) \Pi(k^2), \quad (7.8)$$

$$= -Z(d - 1)k^2 \Pi(k^2). \quad (7.9)$$

Switching around the equation, and expanding K_μ^μ in terms of the expression from Eq.(7.5), we arrive at the following expression for $\Pi(k^2)$,

$$\Pi(k^2) = \frac{-2}{(d-1)Zk^2} Z \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{\text{Tr}[\gamma^\mu (\not{k} + \not{q} + m) \gamma_\mu (\not{q} + m)]}{[(k+q)^2 - m^2][q^2 - m^2]}, \quad (7.10)$$

where an additional factor of 2 is introduced to account for spin. The computation of this integral is slightly involved, and some technical details of the calculations are left to [Appendix C](#). The integral is best tackled in parts, simplifying the numerator and denominators separately, before computing the end product.

We can first simplify the numerator of the integral in Eq.(7.10), by using the identities for Gamma matrices, i.e, d-dimensional Clifford algebra ([Section C.2](#)):

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{Z} &= \text{Tr}[\gamma^\mu(k + q + m)\gamma_\mu(q + m)], \\ &= (8 - 4d)(k + q)(q) + 4dm^2.\end{aligned}\tag{7.11}$$

We can then use the Feynman parametrization technique² to resolve the denominator, i.e,

$$\frac{1}{AB} = \int_0^1 dx \frac{1}{[A + (B - A)x]^2},\tag{7.12}$$

where we have $A = q^2 - m^2$ and $B = (k + q)^2 - m^2$ in our calculations.

Next, we make the following substitutions to bring the integral into a form that is more easily solved [[58](#)]. With $\Delta = q + xk$ and $S = m^2 - x(1 - x)k^2$, the denominator takes the form

$$\frac{1}{AB} = \int_0^1 dx \frac{1}{[\Delta^2 - S]^2}.\tag{7.13}$$

The substitutions also transform the numerator in the following manner in terms of Δ :

$$\mathcal{Z} = (8 - 4d)[\Delta^2 - x(1 - x)k^2 + (1 - 2x)\Delta k] + 4dm^2.\tag{7.14}$$

We can simplify our task further, by identifying the symmetries in the function. We are to integrate over the the entire q -space, and by extension over all values of Δ . The denominator Eq.(7.13) is an even function in Δ , while the numerator Eq.(7.14) contains an odd function in Δ . This means that the net contribution of the integral with respect to the $(1 - 2x)k\Delta$ term from the numerator is zero. This leads us to a more easily solvable integral

$$\Pi(k^2) = \frac{-8}{(d - 1)k^2} \int_0^1 dx \int \frac{d^d \Delta}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{(2 - d)[\Delta^2 - x(1 - x)k^2] + m^2 d}{[\Delta^2 - S]^2}.\tag{7.15}$$

To evaluate this integral, we are in need of particular solutions to integrals of the form

$$J(a, b) = \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{[q^2]^a}{[q^2 - S]^b},\tag{7.16}$$

² Described in further detail in [Section B.1](#).

for $b = 2$ and $a = 0, 1$. The complete calculation of this integral is shown in [Section C.4](#). Upon simplification, it leads to a quantity in terms of the Gamma function [2]:

$$J(a, b) = \frac{(-S)^{a-b} S^{\frac{d}{2}}}{i 2^d \pi^{\frac{d}{2}}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(b - a - \frac{d}{2}) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2} + a)}{\Gamma(b) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}. \quad (7.17)$$

Finally, since we are in $(2 + 1)D$, substituting $d = 3$, we get

$$\Pi(k^2) = 4 \int_0^1 dx [J(1, 2) - J(0, 2)[x(1-x)k^2 + 3m^2]]. \quad (7.18)$$

Substituting the values $a = 0, 1$ and $b = 2$, we get the following values for the function:

$$J(1, 2) = \frac{-3i\sqrt{S}}{8\pi}, \quad J(0, 2) = \frac{-i}{8\pi\sqrt{S}}, \quad (7.19)$$

leading to

$$\Pi(k^2) = \frac{-2i}{\pi k^2} \int_0^1 dx [\sqrt{S} + m^2 \sqrt{S^{-1}}]. \quad (7.20)$$

Bringing everything together we get the following expression for the correlator $K_{\mu\nu}$,

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\mu\nu} &= -Z(k^2 g_{\mu\nu} - k_\mu k_\nu) \Pi(k^2), \\ &= \frac{2iZ}{\pi} \left(g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{k_\mu k_\nu}{k^2} \right) \\ &\quad \cdot \int_0^1 dx \left[\sqrt{m^2 - x(1-x)k^2} + \frac{m^2}{\sqrt{m^2 - x(1-x)k^2}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (7.21)$$

We are dealing with a system with no effective mass, i.e., $m = 0$, which leads to the final expression for the current-current correlator:

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\mu\nu} &= \frac{2iZ}{\pi} \left(g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{k_\mu k_\nu}{k^2} \right) \int_0^1 dx \sqrt{-x(1-x)k^2}, \\ &= \frac{-2Z}{\pi} \left(g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{k_\mu k_\nu}{k^2} \right) |k| \int_0^1 dx \sqrt{x(1-x)}, \\ &= \frac{-Z}{4} \left(g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{k_\mu k_\nu}{k^2} \right) |k| \end{aligned} \quad (7.22)$$

7.1.2 *dc conductivity below the crossover scale*

The dc conductivity $\sigma(\omega)$ can be computed using the Kubo formula³ [1, 16]:

$$\sigma(\omega) = \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} -\frac{K_{\mu\mu}}{i\omega} \quad \mu \in \{1, 2\}. \quad (7.23)$$

For this a required component of the current-current correlation function reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} K_{11} &= \frac{-Z}{4} \left(1 - \frac{k_x^2}{k_x^2 + k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2} \right) \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2}, \\ &= -\frac{Z}{4} \left[\frac{k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2}{\sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (7.24)$$

From this, the dc conductivity for the system at a temperature lower than the cutoff ($\omega < \Omega_c^*$) can be computed:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(\omega) &= \lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \frac{iZ}{4\omega} \left[\frac{k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2}{\sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 - Z^{-2}\omega^2}} \right], \\ &= \frac{i}{4} \frac{Z^{-1}\omega^2}{i|Z^{-1}||\omega|\omega} \end{aligned} \quad (7.25)$$

Upon simplification, we obtain the result

$$\sigma_{dc}(\omega) = \frac{1}{4}. \quad (7.26)$$

This result is identical to the dc conductivity for Dirac fermions. The quasiparticle residue Z (self-consistency factor) plays no role in the conductivity. The finite dc conductivity can be explained due to the net momenta of electrons and holes moving in opposite directions canceling each other out, while the net current generated due to their movement adds up.

7.2 CONDUCTIVITY ABOVE THE CROSSOVER SCALE

In [Chapter 6](#), we verified the ansatz and computed the full propagator in the regime above the crossover scale Ω_c^* :

$$G(i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{-i \operatorname{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{(1 - \alpha)\sqrt{U_c|\omega_{\mathbf{k}}|}}, \quad (7.27)$$

³ An equation that expresses the linear response of an observable quantity due to a time-dependent perturbation.

Figure 7.2: The contribution of the particle-like and hole-like excitations to the total momentum \mathbf{k} and the angular momentum current \mathbf{j} . The particles are moving to the right, while the holes are moving to the left. Their contributions to \mathbf{k} cancel out, while their contributions to \mathbf{j} add.

where α is a constant dependent on the ratio between the crossover scale and SYK interaction strength, with $\alpha = 4[\frac{\pi}{4} - (1 - \log(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*})^{\frac{1}{2}})]$. Here, we follow the ideas outlined in Section 4.3. First, we need to compute the current-current correlator for this regime. On comparing the Feynman diagrams and structure, we can see that it is effectively identical to the calculating the polarization Π_k , as computed in Section 6.2.1 for the bare propagator. Analogous to the aforementioned section, we have

$$\Pi_{\mathbf{k}} = -\frac{1}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \int_{\Omega_c^*}^{U_c} \frac{\text{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) \cdot \text{sgn}(\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}})}{\sqrt{\omega_{\mathbf{q}}(|\omega_{\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{\mathbf{k}}|)}} d\omega_{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (7.28)$$

leading to the solution

$$\Pi_{\mathbf{k}} = -\frac{1}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \log \frac{U_c}{\max\{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}, \Omega_c^*\}}. \quad (7.29)$$

Now, we are restricted to temperatures above the crossover scale $\Omega_c^* < \omega_{\mathbf{k}} < U_c$, so the effective solution is simply

$$\Pi_{\mathbf{k}} = -\frac{1}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \log \frac{U_c}{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}. \quad (7.30)$$

We then compute the dc conductivity by applying the Kubo formula, and neglecting higher orders of $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{-14}$ to obtain

$$\sigma(\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) = \frac{1}{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \frac{-1}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \log \frac{U_c}{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}, \quad (7.31)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} \frac{-1}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \left[\frac{U_c}{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}} - 1 \right], \quad (7.32)$$

$$= \left[\frac{-i}{U_c(1-\alpha)^2} \right] \omega_{\mathbf{k}}^{-1}. \quad (7.33)$$

⁴ When taking the series expansion of $\log x$

Here we see that the conductivity exhibits a $\sigma(\omega) \sim \omega^{-1}$ behaviour or identically, the resistivity shows $\rho(\omega) \sim \omega$. This behaviour is identifiable as a resistivity linear in T , a defining trait of the strange metal phase.

In the next chapter, [Chapter 8](#), these results and ideas related to them are discussed.

CONCLUSION

8.1 DISCUSSION

In this thesis, we constructed a model that shows a crossover between a regime depicting the strange metal phase and a regime where we see behaviour similar to that of Dirac fermions. This model can be solved in the large- N limit. Within our construction where the typical interaction strength is U_c , we find that the system crosses over at a temperature $T \sim \Omega_c^*$, from a low temperature Dirac fermion ground state to a non-Fermi liquid state. If we assume the free electron bandwidth to be W_c , a relationship between the interaction strength and crossover temperature can be $\Omega_c^* \equiv W_c^2/U_c$ [17]. The conductivity crosses over from $\sigma \sim O(1)$ at $T \gg \Omega_c^*$ to the behaviour $\sigma \sim T^{-1}$ at $T \gg \Omega_c^*$; the value of the conductivity at the crossover scale ($T \sim \Omega_c^*$) is $\sigma \approx 1/N$, with all values measured in the units e^2/\hbar .

Some noticeable features of this one band model are as follows: At strong coupling, i.e. $U_c \gg \Omega_c^*$, and at temperatures lower than Ω_c^* , the momentum dependence of the electron self energy is smaller than the frequency dependence. The resulting state is a system containing Dirac cones where the self energy is momentum independent. At temperatures higher than Ω_c^* , the Dirac cones do not exist, and the electronic excitations become incoherent. The resistivity grows linearly with the temperature and does not appear to have a saturation limit, similar to the models studied in [17]. This is in contrast to the model studied in [71], where the resistivity is expected to saturate to a temperature-independent constant due to the presence of strong disorder. Earlier works, [26, 54], considered a model with long-ranged, randomized interactions coupled to a band of itinerant electrons, which also displayed the properties of an intermediate temperature marginal Fermi liquid phase. In the incoherent regime, even when the system is translationally invariant, the previously established mechanism for incoherent transport in disordered SYK-like models [17, 54, 71] continues to be applicable, which can be considered as a result of strong momentum dissipation on the lattice, and the locally critical structure of the correlation functions [33, 34]. Many of the properties of the non-Fermi liquid regime are similar to those found in a few quantum materials. In the Dirac fermion regime, the resistivity is constant, and the numerical factor takes into account the spin and valence degeneracy.

The results add to the discussion of microscopic theories where the existence of momentum dependence of the self energy becomes irrelevant in the large- N limit and strong coupling regime.

8.2 OUTLOOK

We have many avenues to proceed through from here with this model. In this thesis we constructed a one-band model, and the next logical step would be to consider a two-band version. As seen in [17], the nature of the singularities in the two models show a contrast in the type of non-Fermi liquid regime. It may be possible to see a similar contrast here. In addition, another step would be to consider the calculations for different lattices; systems with a critical Fermi surface were also studied in [17].

Theoretical studies [26] show that these models show a finite zero temperature entropic residue s_0 at the $N \rightarrow \infty$, and then the $T \rightarrow 0$ limit. These entropic residues however, are not experimentally present in the cuprates [64], but can be expected in the ruthenates [34, 55]. This means that the model at hand is not universally applicable, but only a stepping stone towards finding a complete theory of the strange metal regime. We have not considered the effects of doping on the conductivity, and it would be prudent to do so since we can see a wide variety of transitions within an unconventional superconductor (Figure 2.3).

Recently, with the experimental evidence that the strange metal phase is realized in twisted bilayer graphene [13, 15], an interesting prospect would be to test whether the lattice based SYK models can imitate this phenomenon. It is quite clear that quasiparticle based studies will not be sufficient in this case.

In the end, studying quantum matter is an important problem in condensed matter physics and there are plenty of interesting questions to ponder.

Part III

APPENDIX

SCHWINGER-DYSON EQUATIONS FOR AN SYK HYPER-LATTICE WITH HOPPING

In this appendix, we show that the Schwinger-Dyson equations for a translationally invariant model of an SYK hyper-lattice remains the same as of those for a single SYK dot. The calculations and discussion of this section follow closely the explanations of Chowdhury et al in [17].

To derive the Schwinger-Dyson Equations for the SYK Model, we start with the action of the system. With the Hamiltonian for the model in Eq.(5.1), we can write down the action for such an interaction¹ as

$$S = \int d\tau \sum_{\mathbf{r},i} c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger (\partial_\tau - \mu) c_{\mathbf{r}i} + t_c \sum_{\langle \mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}' \rangle, i} (c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau) + c_{\mathbf{r}'i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}i}(\tau)) \\ + \int d\tau \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} \sum_{ijkl} J_{ij;kl}^c c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}j}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}k} c_{\mathbf{r}l}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

We now shift to a path-integral formulation of the above model. This allows us to derive the self-consistency equations as a saddle point approximation to the integral that becomes exact in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit. The partition function is given by the imaginary-time path integral

$$Z = \int \mathcal{D}c e^{-S_0[c] - S_U[c]}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$S_0[c] = \int d\tau \sum_{\mathbf{r},i} c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger (\partial_\tau - \mu) c_{\mathbf{r}i} + t_c \sum_{\langle \mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}' \rangle, i} (c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau) + c_{\mathbf{r}'i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}i}(\tau)), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$S_{\text{SYK}}[c] = \int d\tau \frac{1}{(2N)^{3/2}} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} \sum_{ijkl} J_{ij;kl}^c c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}j}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{r}k} c_{\mathbf{r}l}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

To deal with the SYK interactions, it would be prudent to average over their probability distribution. This should be done using replicas. However, it is known from previous analysis of the SYK model [54, 66] and as demonstrated in [17], the self-averaging behaviour of the SYK model allows us to simply utilize the average over single replica to extract the physical properties of interest. Simply put, we can average directly over the partition function to

¹ Refer to Chapter 4 in [1] for the details of such a computation.

extract the physical properties. We therefore just have to manipulate \bar{Z} . After performing a disorder average, we find

$$\bar{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}c e^{-S_0[c] - S_{\text{int}}[c]} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$S_0[c] = \int d\tau \sum_{\mathbf{r}, i} c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger (\partial_\tau - \mu) c_{\mathbf{r}i} + t_c \sum_{\langle \mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}' \rangle, i} (c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau) + c_{\mathbf{r}'i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}i}(\tau)), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$S_{\text{int}}[c] = -\frac{J_c^2}{4N^3} \int d\tau d\tau' \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} \left| \sum_i c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau) \right|^4 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

It is important to note that J_{ijkl}^c being an independent variable on \mathbf{r} leads to a summation over all pairs of lattice sites \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}' in the action term describing the disorder averaged interaction, S_{int} . If instead J_c was an independent random variable at different sites, S_{int} would have only involved on-site interactions, i.e., no sum over lattice sites.

We now define the function $G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau)$ through

$$G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

This term looks similar to the Green's function and will be found to be the same. Inserting the resolution of identity defined by manipulating the above equation:

$$1 = \int \mathcal{D}G \delta\left(G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau)\right) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

into the path integral, allows us to rewrite the delta function as

$$\delta\left(G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau)\right) = \int \mathcal{D}\Sigma e^{\int d\tau d\tau' \Sigma(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) (NG(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) - \sum_i c_{\mathbf{r}i}^\dagger(\tau) c_{\mathbf{r}'i}(\tau))}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The disorder averaged interaction term can be expressed directly in terms of G as

$$S_{\text{int}} = -\frac{NJ_c^2}{4} \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} \int d\tau d\tau' |G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau)|^4. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

We now have a quadratic fermion integral after these manipulations. Now, evaluating this integral gives us an expression for \bar{Z} :

$$\bar{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}G \mathcal{D}\Sigma e^{-Ns[G,\Sigma]}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\begin{aligned} S[G,\Sigma] = & \text{Tr} \ln(\partial_\tau - \mu + \Sigma) - \frac{J_c^2}{4} \int d\tau d\tau' \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} |G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau)|^4 \\ & + \int d\tau d\tau' \sum_{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'} \Sigma(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

In the disorder averaged partition function, the action now has an overall factor of N multiplying it. This means that, when we take the large- N limit, we are essentially performing a saddle-point approximation. The integrals with respect to G and Σ can be easily calculated. Taking the derivative of the action with respect to G and Σ lead to the saddle-point equations, which can be easily identified as the Schwinger-Dyson equations described in [Section 3.2](#). $S[G,\Sigma]$ directly gives us the Luttinger-Ward functional for this model [17].

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) = -J_c^2 G^2(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) G(\mathbf{r}, \tau; \mathbf{r}', \tau'), \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$G(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau) = \frac{1}{\partial_\tau - \mu + \Sigma(\mathbf{r}', \tau'; \mathbf{r}, \tau)}. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

TECHNICAL DETAILS FROM THE CALCULATION OF THE SELF ENERGY

B.1 FEYNMAN PARAMETRIZATION

Feynman parametrization is a technique that is used for evaluating loop integrals [58] which typically arise from Feynman diagrams. These integrals appear quite frequently in quantum field theory. The most simple integral is of the form that appeared in computation of the current-current correlator in [Chapter 7](#):

$$\frac{1}{AB} = \int_0^1 dx \frac{1}{[A(1-x) + Bx]^2}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

This solution can be derived in the following manner:

$$\frac{1}{AB} = \frac{1}{A-B} \left(\frac{1}{A} - \frac{1}{B} \right), \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$= \frac{1}{A-B} \int_B^A \frac{dz}{z^2}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Making a linear transformation on the integral using the following substitution,

$$x = \frac{z-B}{A-B} \implies dx = \frac{dz}{A-B} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

and we have $z = xA + (1-x)B$. We end up with the result for Feynman parameterization:

$$\frac{1}{AB} = \int_0^1 dx \frac{1}{[A(1-x) + Bx]^2}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The more general case can be described using the Dirac delta function [2]:

$$\frac{1}{A_1 \dots A_n} = (n-1)! \int_0^1 dx_1 \dots \int_0^1 dx_n \frac{\delta(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i)}{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i A_i)^n}. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Even more generally, for α_k and $1 \leq k \leq n$:

$$\frac{1}{A_1^{\alpha_1} \dots A_n^{\alpha_n}} = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n)}{\Gamma(\alpha_1) \dots \Gamma(\alpha_n)} \int_0^1 dx_1 \dots \int_0^1 dx_n \frac{\delta(1 - \sum_{i=k}^n x_k) x_1^{\alpha_1-1} \dots x_n^{\alpha_n-1}}{(\sum_{k=1}^n x_k A_k)^{\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k}}, \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where the Gamma function¹, $\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty x^{z-1} e^{-x} dx$, is used.

¹ $\Re(z) > 0$

B.2 DENOMINATOR SIMPLIFICATION

Here, the steps presented help simplify the denominator of our integral in Eq.(6.13) into a form with no product of the integration variables, \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} , appearing:

$$\begin{aligned} & x\mathbf{q}^2 + y\mathbf{p}^2 + z(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2, \\ & = (x+z)\mathbf{q}^2 + (y+z)\mathbf{p}^2 + z\mathbf{k}^2 + 2z(\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{k}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & = (x+z)\left[\mathbf{q} + \frac{z}{x+z}(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})\right]^2 - \frac{z^2}{x+z}(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2 \\ & \quad + (y+z)\mathbf{p}^2 + z\mathbf{k}^2 - 2z\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{k}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & = (x+z)\mathbf{q}^2 + \left(y+z - \frac{z^2}{x+z}\right)\mathbf{p}^2 + \left(\frac{2z^2}{x+z} - 2z\mathbf{k}\right)\mathbf{p} \\ & \quad + \left(z - \frac{z^2}{x+z}\right)\mathbf{k}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & = (x+z)\mathbf{q}^2 + \frac{xy + yz + zx}{x+z}\left[\mathbf{p} - \frac{xz}{xy + yz + zx}\mathbf{k}\right]^2 \\ & \quad - \left(\frac{x^2z^2}{(x+z)(xy + yz + zx)} - \frac{xz}{x+z}\right)\mathbf{k}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

In the above lines of calculation, we make the following substitutions:

$$\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q} + \frac{z}{x+z}(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k}); \quad \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p} - \frac{xz}{xz + xy + yz}\mathbf{k}. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

We then arrive at the following result

$$\begin{aligned} & x\mathbf{q}^2 + y\mathbf{p}^2 + z(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{k})^2 = \\ & \quad (x+z)\mathbf{q}^2 + \frac{xy + yz + zx}{x+z}\mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{xyz}{xy + yz + zx}\mathbf{k}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

with which we continue the calculation from Eq.(6.14).

B.3 EVALUATION OF THE OFF-DIAGONAL ELEMENTS OF GREEN'S FUNCTION

The following calculation is a simple overview of evaluating the dependence of the self energy $\Sigma^{12/21}$ on the momentum variable k_x . We perform this calculation by switching to polar coordinates due to the ease of computation.

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Sigma_0^{12/21}}{\partial k_x} \right|_{k_x=0} = -U_c^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial k_x} \iiint_{q,p,\omega_q,\omega_p,\theta,\phi} qp \frac{qe^{\pm i\theta} \cdot pe^{\pm i\phi}}{(\omega_q^2 + q^2)(\omega_p^2 + p^2)} \cdot \frac{(qe^{\pm i\theta} + pe^{\pm i\phi} - (k_x \pm ik_y))}{[(\omega_q + \omega_p - \omega_k)^2 + (q + p - k)^2]} \Big|_{k_x=0}, \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Sigma_0^{12/21}}{\partial k_x} \right|_{k_x=0} = -U_c^2 \iiint_{q,p,\omega_q,\omega_p,\theta,\phi} qp \frac{qe^{\pm i\theta} \cdot pe^{\pm i\phi}}{(\omega_q^2 + q^2)(\omega_p^2 + p^2)} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial k_x} \frac{(-k_x)}{[(\omega_q + \omega_p - \omega_k)^2 + (q + p - k)^2]} \Big|_{k_x=0}, \quad (\text{B.15})$$

$$= -U_c^2 \iiint_{q,p,\omega_q,\omega_p,\theta,\phi} qp \frac{qe^{\pm i\theta} \cdot pe^{\pm i\phi}}{(\omega_q^2 + q^2)(\omega_p^2 + p^2)} \cdot \frac{2k_x(q_x + p_x - k_x)}{[(\omega_q + \omega_p - \omega_k)^2 + (q + p - k)^2]} \Big|_{k_x=0}, \quad (\text{B.16})$$

$$= 0. \quad (\text{B.17})$$

B.4 COMPUTATION OF SELF ENERGY ABOVE CROSSOVER SCALE

Here, the minor details of the computation of the self energy above the crossover scale as seen in [Section 6.2.2](#) have been penciled in. Evaluating the sgn function and splitting the integral, we have

$$\Sigma_0 = \int_{\omega_q} \frac{i}{U_c} \log \left[\frac{U_c}{\omega_q} \right] \cdot \frac{U_c^2 \cdot \text{sgn}(\omega_q - \omega_k)}{\sqrt{U_c} |\omega_q - \omega_k|}, \quad (\text{B.18})$$

$$= \int_{\omega_k}^{U_c} \frac{i\sqrt{U_c}}{\sqrt{\omega_q - \omega_k}} \left[\log \frac{U_c}{\omega_q} \right] d\omega_q - \int_{\Omega_c^*}^{\omega_k} \frac{i\sqrt{U_c}}{\sqrt{\omega_k - \omega_q}} \left[\log \frac{U_c}{\omega_q} \right] d\omega_q. \quad (\text{B.19})$$

Performing the integral,

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0 = i\sqrt{U_c} & \left(\left[2\sqrt{\omega_q - \omega_k} (2 + \log \frac{U_c}{\omega_q}) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - 4\sqrt{\omega_k} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\omega_q - \omega_k}}{\sqrt{\omega_k}} \right) \right] \Big|_{\omega_k}^{U_c} + \left[2\sqrt{\omega_k - \omega_q} (2 + \log \frac{U_c}{\omega_q}) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - 4\sqrt{\omega_k} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\omega_k - \omega_q}}{\sqrt{\omega_k}} \right) \right] \Big|_{\Omega_c^*}^{\omega_k} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0 = 2i\sqrt{U_c} & \left(2\sqrt{U_c - \omega_k} - 2\sqrt{\omega_k - \Omega_c^*} - \sqrt{\omega_k - \Omega_c^*} [\log \frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*}] \right. \\ & \left. + 2\sqrt{\omega_k} \left[\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\omega_k - \Omega_c^*}}{\sqrt{\omega_k}} \right) - \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{U_c - \omega_k}}{\sqrt{\omega_k}} \right) \right] \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

Since we are in the regime where $\Omega_c^* \ll \omega_k < U_c$, we can use the relevant Taylor series expansions for $\tan^{-1}(\sqrt{\pm[1-x]})$ around suitable points, to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_0 = 4i\sqrt{U_c}\sqrt{\omega_k} & \left[\sqrt{\frac{U_c}{\omega_k} - 1} - \sqrt{1 - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{\omega_k}} - \frac{1}{2} [\log \frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*}] \sqrt{1 - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{\omega_k}} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{4\omega_k} - \frac{\Omega_c^{*2}}{8\omega_k^2} + \mathcal{O}(\omega_k^{-3}) - (\frac{U_c}{\omega_k} - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{3} (\frac{U_c}{\omega_k} - 1)^{\frac{3}{2}} + \mathcal{O}(\omega_k^{-\frac{5}{2}}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.22})$$

$$= 4i\sqrt{U_c}\sqrt{\omega_k} \left[\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{4\omega_k} - (1 - \log(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*})^{\frac{1}{2}}) [1 - \frac{\Omega_c^*}{2\omega_k}] \right] + \mathcal{O}(\omega_k^{-2}) \quad (\text{B.23})$$

Being in the high frequency limit, we can neglect the lower orders of ω_k we find the following relationship for self energy:

$$\Sigma_0 = 4i\sqrt{U_c}\sqrt{\omega_k} \left[\frac{\pi}{4} - (1 - \log(\frac{U_c}{\Omega_c^*})^{\frac{1}{2}}) \right]. \quad (\text{B.24})$$

TECHNICAL DETAILS FROM THE CALCULATION OF THE CONDUCTIVITY

C.1 CONSERVATION OF CURRENT

As mentioned in [Section 7.1.1](#), the current J_μ is a conserved quantity. This means that it satisfies a continuity equation, which in momentum space can be written as $\partial_\mu J^\mu = 0$ [77]. This leads to the following result for the current-current correlator, which allows us to make the ansatz in Eq.(7.10). Introducing k^μ as $(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q} - m) - (\mathbf{q} - m)$ and splitting the fraction into two, we have:

$$k^\mu K_{\mu\nu} = -Z \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{\text{Tr}\{[(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q} - m) - (\mathbf{q} - m)](\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q} + m)\gamma_\nu(\mathbf{q} + m)\}}{[(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q})^2 - m^2][q^2 - m^2]} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

$$= -Z \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \left[\frac{\text{Tr}[\gamma_\nu(\mathbf{q} + m)]}{[q^2 - m^2]} - \frac{\text{Tr}[(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q} + m)\gamma_\nu]}{[(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{q})^2 - m^2]} \right] \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$\stackrel{!}{=} 0. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

This holds because the integral is taken over the entirety of q -space and second fraction in Eq.(C.2) is identical to the first when the substitution $q = \mathbf{k} + q$ is made.

C.2 D-DIMENSIONAL CLIFFORD ALGEBRA

The following are three key properties of a d dimensional Clifford algebra:

$$\gamma_\nu \gamma^\nu = d \cdot \mathbb{1}, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$\gamma^\nu \mathbf{q} \gamma_\nu = 2\mathbf{q} - \gamma^\nu \gamma_\nu \mathbf{q} = (2 - d)\mathbf{q}, \quad (\text{C.5})$$

$$\text{Tr}[\mathbb{1}] = 4, \quad (\text{C.6})$$

where the gamma matrices γ^μ used (cf. [22]) are:

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^1 = \begin{pmatrix} i\sigma_1 & 0 \\ 0 & i\sigma_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} i\sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -i\sigma_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{C.7})$$

C.3 SIMPLIFICATION OF THE NUMERATOR IN THE NUMERICAL POLARIZATION INTEGRAL

Using the Clifford algebra properties listed above, the numerator of $\Pi(k^2)$ can be simplified as:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \text{Tr}[\gamma^\mu(\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{q} + m)\gamma_\mu(\mathcal{q} + m)], \quad (\text{C.8})$$

$$= \text{Tr}[(\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{q})\gamma^\mu \mathcal{q} \gamma_\mu + (\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{q})\gamma_\mu \gamma^\mu m + m\gamma^\mu \mathcal{q} \gamma_\mu + m^2\gamma_\mu \gamma^\mu], \quad (\text{C.9})$$

$$= (2 - d)\text{Tr}[(\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{q})(\mathcal{q})] + 4dm^2, \quad (\text{C.10})$$

$$\mathcal{Z} = (8 - 4d)(k + q)(q) + 4dm^2. \quad (\text{C.11})$$

Here d is the dimension of the concerned system and m represents a effective mass of the particle.

C.4 EVALUATING $J(a, b)$

As seen in [Section 7.1.1](#), we need the particular solutions to integrals of the following type:

$$J(a, b) = \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{[q^2]^a}{[q^2 - S]^b}, \quad (\text{C.12})$$

where $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

To evaluate this, we must first clarify that we have suppressed the contribution of $i\varepsilon$ for brevity. In the denominator we have always had $m^2 \rightarrow m^2 - i\varepsilon$. This determines the pole structure in the q^0 -plane. We first perform a Wick Rotation and rotate the integration contour as

$$q_0 \rightarrow iq_0 \implies dq_0 \rightarrow idq_0; q^2 = q_0^2 - \mathbf{q}^2 \rightarrow -q_E^2 = -(q_0^2 + \mathbf{q}^2) \quad (\text{C.13})$$

where the subscript E denotes the change to a Euclidean Metric. With this, we have

$$J(a, b) = \int \frac{d^d q}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{[q^2]^a}{[q^2 - S]^b} = \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \int \frac{d^d q_E}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{[q_E^2]^a}{[q_E^2 - S]^b}, \quad (\text{C.14})$$

$$= \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \int \frac{d\Omega_{d-1}}{(2\pi)^d} \int_0^\infty dr r^{d-1} \frac{r^{2a}}{(r^2 + S)^2}, \quad (\text{C.15})$$

where we have used the fact that $\int d^d q = \int d\Omega_{d-1} \int_0^\infty dr r^{d-1}$. Further, using the substitution $t = \frac{r^2}{S}$ we get

$$J(a, b) = \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \frac{2\pi^{\frac{d}{2}}}{(2\pi)^d \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \int_0^\infty \frac{dr}{S^b} \frac{r^{2a+d-1}}{(r^2/S + 1)^b}, \quad (\text{C.16})$$

$$= \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \frac{2\pi^{\frac{d}{2}}}{(2\pi)^d \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} S^{\frac{d}{2}+a-b} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^{\frac{d}{2}+a-1}}{2(1+t)^b} dt, \quad (\text{C.17})$$

where $\int d\Omega_{d-1} = 2\pi^{\frac{d}{2}} [\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})]^{-1}$. Finally, we make the substitution $y = (1+t)^{-1}$ to get

$$J(a, b) = \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \frac{2\pi^{\frac{d}{2}}}{2(2\pi)^d \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} S^{\frac{d}{2}+a-b} \int_0^1 dy (1-y)^{\frac{d}{2}+a-1} y^{b-\frac{d}{2}-a-1}, \quad (\text{C.18})$$

$$= \frac{(-1)^{a-b}}{i} \frac{\pi^{\frac{d}{2}}}{(2\pi)^d \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} S^{\frac{d}{2}+a-b} B[(b-a-\frac{d}{2}), (\frac{d}{2}+a)]. \quad (\text{C.19})$$

Here we can identify the integral of the form $B(a, b) = \int_0^1 dy (1-y)^{b-1} y^{a-1}$ as the Beta function which is related to the Gamma function as $B(x, y) = \frac{\Gamma(x)\Gamma(y)}{\Gamma(x+y)}$. Simplified, $J(a, b)$ evaluates to

$$J(a, b) = \frac{(-S)^{a-b} S^{\frac{d}{2}}}{i 2^d \pi^{\frac{d}{2}}} \cdot \frac{\Gamma(b-a-\frac{d}{2})\Gamma(\frac{d}{2}+a)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}. \quad (\text{C.20})$$

The Gamma function is defined through the following integral, $\Gamma(z) = \int_0^\infty x^{z-1} e^{-x} dx$.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis is my own work, and that I have not used any sources or aids other than those stated in the thesis.

Munich, October 31st 2019

Koushik Swaminathan